

**THE LAND USE ACT AND PRIVATE PROPRIETARY
RIGHTS: ISSUES & PROSPECTS**

BY

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**BEING A RESEARCH PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE
FACULTY OF LAW IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF THE
REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF THE MASTER OF
LAWS (LL.M) DEGREE OF THE UNIVERSITY OF LAGOS,
AKOKA**

NOVEMBER, 2025

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the project work titled “**THE LAND USE ACT AND PRIVATE PROPRIETARY RIGHTS: ISSUES & PROSPECTS**” being a Research Project submitted to the Faculty of Law in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the Master of Laws (LL.M) Degree of the University of Lagos, Akoka and submitted to the Faculty of Law, LLM, University of Lagos, Akoka; is a record of original work done by me and under the guidance of Professor Akintunde K. Otubu, Professor of Property Law, Faculty of Law, University of Lagos, Akoka.

The results so contained in this thesis have not been submitted to any other institute or Post-graduate programme for the award of any degree.

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this Research Project titled “*The Land Use Act and Private Proprietary Rights: Issues & Prospects*” was written by **Titus, Gift Ekanem** with Matriculation Number **219061289** under my supervision.

Professor Akintunde K. Otubu
Supervisor

20-11-2025

Date

DEDICATION

To my persistence, consistence and refueling drive in pursuit of my programme, though the road had lots of impediments but same was surmounted; likewise, the spirit of financial responsibility in attaining my set goals and frugal in financial commitments.

In all sincerity, my appreciation and dedication go to my No. 1 support system and encouragement in the person of Chief Azes Ahmed Giwa Esq. LL.B, BL, LL.M, whom initially recognized the zeal in me and refined same, encouraging me to pursue my dreams and aspirations.

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TABLE OF CASES

1. Udeze V. Chidebe (1990) 1 NWLR (PT. 125) 141 at 162.
2. Buraimoh v Bamgbose (1988) LCN/2401(SC).
3. Amodu Tijani v Secretary, Southern Nigeria (1921) AC 399.
4. Oyewumi v Ogunesan (1990) 3 NWLR (Pt. 137) 182.
5. Savannah Bank v Ajilo (1989) 1 NWLR (Pt. 97) 305.
6. Nkwocha v Governor of Anambra State (1984) 6 SC 362.
7. Ogunleye v Oni (1990) 2 NWLR (Pt. 135) 745.
8. *Fibrosa Spolka Akcyjna v Fairbairn Lawson Combe Barbour Ltd* [1943] AC 32.
9. Abiodun v Minister of Lands and Housing (2005) 11 NWLR (Pt. 935) 1.
10. Osho v Foreign Finance Corporation (1991) 4 NWLR (Pt. 184) 157.
11. Olatunji v Military Governor of Oyo State (1994) 4 NWLR (Pt 336) 1.
12. Goldmark Nigeria Ltd v Ibafo Co. Ltd (2012) LPELR-9340(SC).
13. A-G Lagos State v Ajayi (2000) 12 NWLR (Pt 682) 509.
14. Ijewere v Igbinovia (1992) 2 NWLR (Pt 226) 578.
15. Bello v Diocesan Synod of Lagos (1973) 3 SC 131.
16. Adole v Gwar (2008) 11 NWLR (Pt 1099) 562.
17. Shell Petroleum Dev. Co. v. Isaiah (2001) FWLR (Pt. 56) 608.
18. Abioye v Yakubu [1991] 5 NWLR (Pt 190) 130.
19. *Akande v Kolere* (1966) NNLR 113.
20. *Union Bank of Nigeria Plc & Another v Ayodare & Sons (Nig) Ltd* (SC. 375/2001) [2007] NGSC 148.
21. *CSS Bookshops Ltd v Registered Trustees of Muslim Community in Rivers State* (2006) 4 SCNJ 310.
22. Dr Abdu-Ho v Mustapha Abubakar & Ors (2016) JELR 33394 (CA).
23. Pastor Ize-Iyamu and I. O. Farms Limited v. Edo State Government (Unreported Suit No:B/637/2021 Judgment Delivered by Hon. Justice Peter Akhihero on 29 Stumper 2024).
24. Awojugbagbe Light Ind Ltd v Chinukwe [1995] 4 NWLR (Pt 390) 379.
25. Ibrahim v Obaje [2019] 3 NWLR (Pt 1660) 389.
26. Lagos State Development and Property Corporation v. Foreign Finance Corporation (1987) 1 NWLR (Pt. 50) 413.

27. Archbishop Anthony Olubunmi Okogie v. Attorney-General of Lagos State (1981) 2 NCLR 337.
28. *Bello v Diocesan Synod of Lagos* (1973) 1 All NLR (Pt. I) 247
29. *Governor of Lagos State v Ojukwu* (1986) 1 NWLR (Pt. 18) 621.
30. *Obikoya & Sons Ltd v Governor of Lagos State* (1987) 1 NWLR (Pt 50) 385 C.A.
31. *Attorney-General of Lagos State v Attorney-General of the Federation* (2003) 12 NWLR (Pt 833) 1.
32. *Rylands V. Fletcher* 1868 UKHL LR 3 HL 3
33. *Pastor Ize-Iyamu and I. O. Farms Limited v. Edo State Government* (Unreported Suit No:B/637/2021 Judgment Delivered by Hon. Justice Peter Akhiero on 29 Stumper 2024).

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

1. LUA - Land Use Act
2. S. - Section
3. CFRN - Constitution of The Federal Republic of Nigeria
4. No. - Number
5. LTD. - Limited
6. Co. - Corporation
7. SRO - Statutory Right of Occupancy
8. C of O - Certificate of Occupancy
9. ACHPR - African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights
10. PTCLR - Presidential Technical Committee on Land Reform
11. LRL - Land Registration Law
12. ALT - The Aboriginal Land Trust
13. AAPA - Aboriginal Affairs Planning Authority Act
14. AG - Attorney-General
15. JDA - Joint Development Agreement
16. PCL - Property and Conveyancing Law

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ABSTRACT

The Land Use Act of 1978 was enacted as a bold legislative intervention aimed at restructuring Nigeria's land tenure system by vesting all land in each state in the Governor, to be held in trust for the people. While the Act sought to democratize access to land and eliminate the chaos of multiple tenure regimes, it has generated significant controversy over its implications for private proprietary rights. This study examines the tensions between state control under the Land Use Act and the protection of individual rights to land, exploring the historical, legal, and practical dimensions of land administration in Nigeria. The research adopts a doctrinal methodology, examining constitutional provisions, statutory frameworks, case law, and scholarly commentaries to analyze how the Act has affected the security of land tenure, the doctrine of estates, compensation for expropriation, and the recognition of customary landholding systems. The study finds that the discretionary powers of governors, the weak legal protection of customary interests, vague definitions of public purpose, and inadequate compensation procedures all contribute to the erosion of proprietary rights. It further observes that these shortcomings hinder equitable access to land, discourage investment, and fuel socio-economic discontent. Based on these findings, the study recommends five key reforms: limiting discretionary powers of governors, codifying customary land rights, clarifying the meaning of public purpose, improving compensation mechanisms, and modernizing the Land Use Act through constitutional review. These reforms are essential to create a land governance framework that respects proprietary rights while promoting national development and justice.

Keywords: Land Use Act, Proprietary rights, Land tenure, Compensation, Customary land rights, Public purpose, Land reform.

CHAPTER ONE

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.0 Background to the Study

Land, as a fundamental asset, holds profound significance in the socio-economic and political fabric of any nation. In Nigeria, land transcends its physical attributes to embody cultural identity, social status, and economic power.¹ The proprietary rights of individuals in land are not merely legal constructs but are pivotal in shaping the nation's economic trajectory. Secure land rights empower individuals, foster investment, and catalyze economic development. Conversely, ambiguous or insecure land tenure systems can stifle growth, breed conflicts, and perpetuate poverty.²

Historically, Nigeria's land tenure systems have been a mixture of customary practices and colonial legacies. Before colonial intervention, land was predominantly held communally, with traditional leaders overseeing its allocation and use. These customary systems, while adaptable, often lacked formal recognition, leading to challenges in land transactions and disputes. The colonial era introduced statutory land laws, which coexisted with customary practices, creating a duality that complicated land administration.³

The promulgation of the Land Use Act (LUA) in 1978⁴ marked a significant shift in Nigeria's land governance. The Act vested all land within a state's territory in the hands of the state governor, to be held in trust for the people.⁵ This centralization aimed to streamline land administration, curb speculation, and ensure equitable access. However, the LUA's

¹ C.C. Opata & O. Asogwa, "Title, Rituals, and Land Use: The Heritage of a Nigerian Society." (2017) 7(2) *Sage Open* 2158244016689129.

² F.k. Upham, "The Paradoxical Roles of Property Rights in Growth and Development." (2015) 8(2) *Law and Development Review* 253-269.

³ T.O. Elias, *Nigerian Land Law and Custom* (Online: Taylor & Francis, 2024) 2.

⁴ Land Use Act, Cap L5, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria (LFN) 2004.

⁵ *Ibid*, s. 1.

implementation has been fraught with challenges. The requirement for governor's consent in land transactions, as stipulated in Section 22 of the LUA, has introduced bureaucratic bottlenecks, increased transaction costs, and provided avenues for corruption.⁶

Moreover, the provisions of the LUA have consistently been at odds with Nigeria's deep-rooted customary land tenure systems, creating a persistent dichotomy that continues to generate legal uncertainty and socio-political tension. Despite the LUA's objective of unifying land tenure under statutory control, customary landholding systems remain predominant, particularly in rural communities where land is traditionally regarded as communal heritage held in trust by family heads, chiefs, or community leaders. These customary structures are often unwritten but are culturally entrenched, governing the distribution, use, and inheritance of land.⁷

The imposition of statutory mechanisms, such as the requirement for the governor's consent before any alienation of land, is largely incompatible with these traditional systems. This has resulted in a duality of authority, where traditional leaders and statutory institutions claim overlapping control, leading to disputes and, in some cases, violent confrontations. Vulnerable groups, especially women and indigenous populations, often suffer the most under this legal ambiguity. Customary systems tend to marginalize women from land ownership, limiting their economic autonomy. This conflict not only undermines social cohesion but also hampers the realization of land reforms aimed at equitable access and sustainable development.⁸

The economic consequences of these legal and administrative challenges under the LUA are far-reaching and detrimental to national development. Secure and well-defined land rights form the foundation of economic empowerment, enabling individuals and businesses to make long-

⁶ A. Otubu, "The Land Use Act and Land Administration in 21st Century Nigeria: Need for Reforms." (2018) 9(1) *Journal of Sustainable Development Law and Policy* 80-108.

⁷ K.H. Babalola & S.A. Hull, "Examining the Land Use Act of 1978 and Its Effects on Tenure Security in Nigeria: A Case Study of Ekiti State, Nigeria." (2019) 22(1) *Potchefstroom Electronic Law Journal* 1-14.

⁸ F. Obeng-Odoom, "Land Reforms in Africa: Theory, Practice, and Outcome" (2016) 49(5) *Habitat International* 923.

term investments in real estate, agriculture, and industrial ventures. When land tenure is insecure or uncertain, potential investors are discouraged due to the heightened risk of disputes, expropriation, or procedural delays.⁹ In Nigeria, the requirement for governor’s consent, bureaucratic inefficiencies, and outdated land registries collectively render land transactions cumbersome and costly. This has a direct impact on agricultural productivity, as farmers are reluctant to invest in long-term land improvement without assurance of tenure.¹⁰

In urban areas, uncertainty in land ownership hinders infrastructure development and contributes to the proliferation of informal settlements. Moreover, the inability to use land as collateral due to the lack of formal title documents severely restricts access to finance, especially for small and medium enterprises. According to the World Bank’s *Doing Business* report, Nigeria ranks poorly in property registration indicators, with the process marked by lack of transparency, high costs, and prolonged timelines.¹¹ Addressing these economic inefficiencies requires urgent reform to enhance tenure security and streamline land administration processes.

Furthermore, the LUA’s framework for land revocation—particularly under Section 28, which permits compulsory acquisition of land for overriding public interest—has been subject to intense criticism for its susceptibility to misuse and lack of procedural safeguards. While the intention behind this provision is to enable governments to facilitate development projects such as roads, schools, and hospitals, in practice, the process has often been shrouded in opacity and administrative arbitrariness. Many instances have been reported where land has been acquired

⁹ M.E. Nwocha, “Impact of the Nigerian Land Use Act on Economic Development in the Country.” (2016) 8(2) *Acta Universitatis Danubius. Administratio* 117-128.

¹⁰ M.E. Nwocha, Note 9.

¹¹ World Bank, *Doing Business 2020: Comparing Business Regulation in 190 Economies* (World Bank Group, 2020) <https://www.doingbusiness.org/content/dam/doingBusiness/media/Annual-Reports/English/DB2020-report_web-version.pdf> accessed 15 May 2025.

ostensibly for public purposes, only to be subsequently reallocated to private developers or influential individuals, raising concerns about transparency and fairness.¹²

The requirement of compensation for compulsorily acquired lands, though present in the law, is frequently undermined by delays, undervaluation of land, or outright denial of rightful claims. Affected individuals, particularly those from low-income or rural backgrounds, often lack the legal literacy or financial capacity to challenge such actions in court.¹³ This not only erodes public trust in land governance but also violates the constitutional guarantee of property rights under Section 44 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended) (CFRN).¹⁴ Without robust enforcement mechanisms, clear definitions of “public purpose,” and transparent compensation procedures, the provision continues to be an instrument of disenfranchisement rather than a tool for equitable development.¹⁵

In light of these challenges, there is a pressing need to re-examine the proprietary rights of individuals in land within Nigeria. Strengthening these rights is not only a matter of legal reform but also a catalyst for economic prosperity. By ensuring secure and equitable land tenure, Nigeria can unlock the potential of its land resources, promote inclusive development, and foster social stability.

¹² O.O. Makinde, & O.T. Makinde, “Public Land Acquisition and Administration in Nigeria: Issues, Strategies and Policies.” (2019) 6(7) *Journal of Multidisciplinary Engineering Science and Technology* 10381-10394.

¹³ *Ibid.*

¹⁴ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), Cap C23 LFN 2004 (CFRN).

¹⁵ A. Otubu, ‘The Land Use Act and Land Ownership Debate in Nigeria: A Critical Review: Resolving the Impasse’ (SSRN Electronic Journal, 2015) <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/272173374_The_Land_Use_Act_and_Land_Ownership_Debate_in_Nigeria_Resolving_the_Impasse> accessed 15 May 2025.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Land remains one of the most significant and finite resources in any economy. In Nigeria, access to land and the proprietary rights associated with it are central to individual wealth, socio-economic development, and national prosperity. However, the legal framework governing land ownership and proprietary rights is fraught with complexities, ambiguities, and inconsistencies. The introduction of the LUA, while aimed at harmonizing land administration, centralized control in the hands of state governors and created bureaucratic barriers that have often undermined the full realization of individual land rights. Consequently, there is a continuing tension between traditional ownership rights, statutory rights under the Act, and the economic benefits that should accrue from land ownership.

The concentration of ownership and control in the hands of the state has led to several issues, including unclear titling, insecure tenure, and restricted transferability of land. These limitations have stifled the ability of individuals to leverage land as a productive asset, especially in rural and semi-urban areas. Additionally, the process of acquiring land legally is often cumbersome, costly, and plagued by corruption. The denial or revocation of proprietary rights without adequate compensation further alienates individuals and discourages private investment. This scenario raises fundamental legal, economic, and human rights questions about the effectiveness of Nigeria's land administration framework in promoting individual prosperity.

Moreover, there is a growing concern about how proprietary rights in land can serve as a catalyst for economic growth, especially in the context of real estate development, agricultural productivity, and access to credit. The absence of a reliable and enforceable land tenure system that guarantees proprietary rights undermines confidence in property markets and restricts economic opportunities for individuals. Therefore, there is an urgent need to assess how

proprietary land rights can be restructured or better protected to foster prosperity and inclusive economic development in Nigeria.

1.2 Aims and Objectives of the Study

The principal aim of this study is to examine the proprietary rights of individuals in land and evaluate their relevance to economic prosperity in Nigeria. The specific objectives are as follows:

1. To explore the historical and legal foundations of proprietary rights in land in Nigeria.
2. To examine the implications of the Land Use Act on individual proprietary rights.
3. To investigate how proprietary rights in land contribute to economic development.
4. To identify the legal and administrative challenges that undermine proprietary land rights.
5. To make comparative assessments with other jurisdictions and recommend reforms for strengthening proprietary rights and enhancing prosperity.

1.3 Research Question

This research will be guided by the following questions:

1. What are the legal foundations and philosophical justifications for proprietary rights in land?
2. How does the Land Use Act affect the proprietary rights of individuals in Nigeria?
3. In what ways do proprietary rights in land contribute to economic prosperity?
4. What are the challenges faced by landholders in exercising proprietary rights in Nigeria?
5. What lessons can Nigeria draw from other jurisdictions in enhancing property rights in land?

1.4 Research Methodology

This study adopts a doctrinal legal research methodology. It involves a critical examination of primary sources such as statutes, judicial decisions, and constitutional provisions, particularly the LUA and the 1999 CFRN. Secondary sources including journal articles, textbooks, and commentaries will also be analyzed to provide theoretical and contextual insights. Comparative analysis will be employed to evaluate property rights regimes in selected jurisdictions like the United Kingdom and Australia, in order to draw lessons relevant to the Nigerian context.

1.5 Significance of the Study

The significance of this study lies in its contribution to understanding the critical nexus between proprietary rights in land and economic prosperity in Nigeria. Land remains one of the most essential factors of production, and access to secure land rights directly influences individuals' ability to engage in productive activities such as agriculture, real estate development, and industrialization. In a country where land disputes are rampant and tenure insecurity is common, this research sheds light on how clear, enforceable proprietary rights can enhance individual economic empowerment and reduce poverty. By examining the legal structures and frameworks governing land ownership, the study provides a lens through which the practical economic benefits of land rights can be fully appreciated.

Additionally, the study has significant legal relevance, particularly in assessing the effectiveness and impact of the LUA and other land-related statutes. Given the centralized control of land under the Nigerian legal framework, the study critically evaluates how the vesting of land in the Governor under the LUA has affected proprietary interests, especially in terms of access, control, transferability, and compensation. This is important for legal reform, as it highlights both the constraints and possibilities within the current system, and proposes

reforms that can strengthen proprietary rights while balancing public interest considerations such as eminent domain.

Lastly, this study is important for policymakers, legal practitioners, investors, and scholars. For policymakers, it offers valuable insights into the potential of property rights as a tool for driving inclusive economic development. For legal practitioners, it deepens the understanding of land tenure issues and helps identify areas needing advocacy or judicial clarification. For investors and development planners, the study identifies how clarity and security in land ownership can foster investment confidence. For scholars, it contributes to the body of knowledge on legal pluralism, land reform, and property law, particularly within the Nigerian and broader African context.

1.6 Scope and Limitation of the Study

This research focuses primarily on proprietary rights in land as they relate to individuals in Nigeria. The study will assess the existing legal framework with particular emphasis on the LUA, customary land tenure systems, and constitutional provisions. The scope includes evaluating the practical operation of these rights and their impact on economic activities such as agriculture, urban development, and investment.

However, the study is limited in its geographical reach and does not provide exhaustive empirical data due to constraints of time and access. While it draws on examples from other jurisdictions for comparison, the emphasis remains on the Nigerian legal and socio-economic context.

1.7 Structure of the Study

The research is organised into five chapters. Chapter One presents the general introduction, including the background, problem statement, objectives, methodology, and structure. Chapter

Two offers a comprehensive literature review and conceptual framework, exploring key terminologies, historical evolution of land rights, and theoretical debates. Chapter Three analyses the legal framework governing proprietary rights under the Land Use Act. Chapter Four discusses challenges and prospects, including comparative insights from other jurisdictions. Chapter Five concludes the research and presents recommendations for reform and implementation.

1.8 Literature Review

A literature review is essential to map existing research, highlight key findings from recent studies, and demonstrate how this study builds on, challenges, or fills gaps in that body of knowledge. Focusing on recent sources ensures current relevance and reflects developments since the LUA's reforms.

Otubu's¹⁶ 2018 analysis provides a critical evaluation of the LUA, identifying its administrative structure as opaque, fragmented, and ill-suited for the demands of 21st-century Nigeria. He advocates for a unified right-of-occupancy regime, the establishment of a single land administration authority, and the removal of the wide discretionary powers of state governors. His work underscores the urgent need for legislative overhaul to enhance administrative clarity and efficiency. While his recommendations are primarily structural, the current study takes this further by exploring how these administrative inconsistencies directly impair the security and clarity of private proprietary rights in Nigeria.

Niyazova and colleagues¹⁷ explore the legal limitations placed on land ownership in the context of balancing public and private interests. They argue that excessive regulatory constraints can

¹⁶ A. Otubu, "The Land Use Act and Land Administration in 21st Century Nigeria: Need for Reforms" (2018) 9(1) *Journal of Sustainable Development Law and Policy* 80-108.

¹⁷ A.N. Niyazova et al., "Land Proprietary Rights and Limitations in Private and Public Interests" (2016) 7(3) *Journal of Advanced Research in Law and Economics* 584-589.

distort land utility and discourage private investment, particularly where proprietary security is weak. Although their work has a broader international scope, it raises important questions about the legitimacy and efficiency of limitations on ownership rights. This study builds on their theoretical foundation by applying the concepts directly to the Nigerian LUA, evaluating how statutory and administrative frameworks hinder proprietary security for landowners.

Babalola and Hull¹⁸ focus on the effects of the LUA on tenure security through a case study in Ekiti State. Their findings show that the Act, by centralising land control in the hands of state governors and requiring Governor's consent for transactions, effectively alienates the rural poor from secure land tenure. Bureaucratic inefficiencies, land speculation, and power asymmetries all contribute to insecurity in land rights. Although they recommend pro-poor policy reforms, the current study extends their work by interrogating the legal and doctrinal bases of these inequalities, aiming to understand how proprietary rights can be better protected under the law.

Ugonabo, Egolom and Sado¹⁹ examine Nigeria's land policy, pointing to persistent challenges arising from the abolition of freehold interests and the heavy administrative burden associated with obtaining Governor's consent. They argue that private ownership remains insecure under the current regime and advocate for constitutional changes to facilitate more adaptive reforms. However, their recommendations lack a detailed legal examination of the consequences of such constitutional amendments. This study contributes to that discourse by exploring both the doctrinal implications and the practical feasibility of constitutional reforms aimed at strengthening private land rights.

¹⁸ K.H. Babalola and SA Hull, "Examining the Land Use Act of 1978 and its Effects on Tenure Security in Nigeria: A Case Study of Ekiti State, Nigeria" (2019) 22(1) *Potchefstroom Electronic Law Journal/Potchefstroomse Elektroniese Regsblad* 21-30.

¹⁹ C.U. Ugonabo, CC Egolom and RO Sado, "Nigerian Land Policy: Issues, Challenges and the Way Forward" (2023) 11(1) *Global Journal of Politics and Law Research* 57-77.

Kasim and Agbola²⁰ highlight a major structural flaw in Nigeria’s land reform—documentation. They observe that only a tiny fraction of land is properly registered, making land rights informal and vulnerable. The failure of administrative systems to provide clear and accessible registration procedures fuels insecurity and obstructs effective land governance. While their work documents the scope of the problem, this study delves deeper into how these failures specifically weaken proprietary claims and limit the enforceability of rights, thereby affecting investment, development, and legal certainty in land transactions.

Mabogunje’s²¹ work charts the slow progress of policy implementation and highlights the fragmentation of reform efforts. He calls for a coherent national land policy that aligns with economic and social objectives. The current study revisits his critique through a contemporary lens, analyzing whether subsequent legal developments have responded to the structural and policy shortcomings he identified. It further evaluates the impact of ongoing administrative dysfunction on proprietary rights within today’s legal environment.

Otubu’s²² earlier work anticipates many of the criticisms that now dominate discourse on the LUA. He identified the risk of excessive bureaucratic control, tenure insecurity, and the need for a comprehensive land reform strategy. The current study builds on his foundational critique by examining what has changed and what remains unaddressed. It evaluates whether reforms undertaken since his writing have enhanced private land security or whether the foundational legal structure of the LUA still impedes meaningful proprietary protection.

²⁰ O.F. Kasim and SB Agbola, “Strategies and Challenges of Land Reform in Nigeria” (2018) 53(2) *Journal of Public Administration* 541-564.

²¹ A.L. Mabogunje, “Land Reform in Nigeria: Progress, Problems & Prospects” In *Annual Conference on Land Policy and Administration* (World Bank, April, 2010) 26.

²² A.K. Otubu, “Land Reforms and the Future of Land Use Act in Nigeria” (2007-2010) *Nigerian Current Law Review* (NIALS) 226-143.

In conclusion, the literature reviewed reveals several recurring concerns lack of administrative clarity, centralization of control, inadequate registration, and tenure insecurity each of which undermines proprietary land rights in Nigeria. However, most of the studies focus either on policy suggestions or general observations without deep doctrinal analysis of the LUA and its statutory implications. Furthermore, the legal feasibility and practical implications of proposed reforms remain under-explored. The current study addresses these gaps by undertaking a doctrinal analysis of key provisions of the LUA, assessing how they affect individual proprietary rights, and proposing legally sound and practically implementable reforms. This approach bridges the gap between academic commentary and actionable legal reform

CHAPTER TWO

HISTORICAL AND LEGAL FOUNDATION OF PROPRIETARY RIGHTS

2.0 Introduction

The concept of proprietary rights in land has remained central to legal, economic, and political discourse across jurisdictions and historical epochs. In the Nigerian context, proprietary rights are not merely legal abstractions but represent a nexus of cultural identity, economic empowerment, social stratification, and political control. Prior to the promulgation of the LUA in 1978, the Nigerian land tenure system was characterized by a multiplicity of landholding structures, including indigenous customary systems and imported English legal doctrines. These systems evolved under the influence of colonial administration, indigenous customary practices, and post-independence reforms, each contributing to the complexity of land ownership and use.

This chapter critically examines the historical and legal foundations of proprietary rights in Nigeria by first laying out key conceptual definitions and theoretical perspectives on property and ownership. It investigates the philosophical basis for private property, the distinction between possessory and proprietary interests, and the pre-LUA structures of landholding. Furthermore, the chapter explores critical legal and economic questions surrounding land as a source of wealth and power, including debates over unjust enrichment, equity in land allocation, and the effects of revocation and acquisition mechanisms. This provides a necessary context for understanding the rationale behind Nigeria's current land regime and the enduring contestations surrounding it.

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Definition of Key Terms: Property, Proprietary Rights, and Land

In jurisprudence, “property” denotes a bundle of legal rights or interests a person holds in a thing. These rights can be tangible, such as land or buildings, or intangible, such as patents, trademarks or copyrights.²³ Within the scope of land law particularly under Nigeria’s LUA “property” is understood narrowly as rights connected to land. These rights include possession, use, transfer, and exclusion of others. Legally, property refers to enforceable interests in land or land-related rights, not the physical item itself.²⁴

The term “land” in Nigeria’s legal system, as shaped by the LUA, has a wide meaning. It encompasses (a) the earth’s surface, (b) anything permanently attached buildings, trees, minerals (with certain statutory exceptions) and (c) incorporeal hereditaments: intangible rights such as easements, covenants, rents, *profits à prendre*, and customary interests. Superficial understanding of land as mere ground is therefore misplaced; land also includes the bundle of rights associated with it, an acknowledgment reflected in Western Region legislation and in judicial pronouncement.²⁵

“Proprietary rights” are a subset of property rights that confer legal ownership or control with enforceable authority, such as the ability to exclude others from trespass, alienate, transfer by lease or sale, mortgage, bequeath, and seek redress for infringement. Unlike mere personal rights (e.g., contractual claims), proprietary rights bind the whole world and are enforceable against all. They are typically inheritable and transferable — key features in facilitating land markets, mortgage lending, and estate planning.²⁶

²³ T.S. Kumari and GI Priyadarsini, “Concept of Property-Jurisprudential Perspective” (2019) *GLS Law Journal* 7-17.

²⁴ I.O. Smith, *Practical Approach to Law of Real Property in Nigeria* (Lagos: Ecowatch Publication Limited, 2007) 2.

²⁵ *Ibid*, 8.

²⁶ *Ibid*, 353.

Under the LUA, land is vested not in individuals but in the Governor of each State, acting in trust for the people.²⁷ Individuals can only hold land via statutory rights of occupancy (urban)²⁸ or customary rights of occupancy (rural),²⁹ both of which are types of proprietary interests akin to long-term leases. These proprietary rights convey the ability to possess, use, and transfer the parcel of land, with appropriate legal formalities.

Thus, "property" becomes the right or interest a person holds; "proprietary rights" signify legally enforceable, transferable, and inheritable interests in land; and "land" comprises both the physical soil and the legal rights tied to it. These definitions form the conceptual bedrock from which subsequent doctrinal and statutory analysis, culminating in the LUA—unfolds.

2.1.2 Philosophical and Legal Foundations of Property Rights

The foundations of property rights can be traced to divergent philosophical and legal schools. On one end, natural law theory, notably John Locke, posits that property rights emerge naturally when individuals mix their labour with natural resources. Locke believed ownership through investment of labour is a natural right derived from individual sovereignty.³⁰ In agricultural societies, especially agrarian contexts, this principle legitimizes claims to land based on use and labour. Philosophical legitimacy in Locke's framework provides a moral counterweight to the state's power, supporting robust property protection enshrined in constitutions like Nigeria's 1999 CFRN.³¹

Conversely, legal positivists such as Jeremy Bentham rejected the idea of natural rights. Bentham viewed property rights as artificial constructs, birthed, defined, and enforced through the authority of the state and its legal institutions. In this view, property exists only by virtue

²⁷ LUA, s. 1.

²⁸ *Ibid*, s. 5(1).

²⁹ *Ibid*, s. 6(1).

³⁰ J. Locke, *Two Treatises of Government* (Peter Laslett edn, Cambridge University Press, 1988) 34.

³¹ CFRN, ss. 43-44.

of state promulgation and legal recognition.³² Nigeria's legal system exemplifies this duality: customary tenure systems, rooted in communal or familial landholding, reflect indigenous, collective approaches grounded in shared historical and social contexts. By contrast, English received law, introduced during colonial rule, promoted individual entitlements such as freehold and leasehold—legally atomized and enforceable under formal institutions.

Customary systems, governed through lineage and traditional leaders, tend to prioritize the collective welfare of communities, whereas Western systems privilege the individual — granting exclusive control through deeds and titles. This tension embodies the philosophical divide: Locke's affirmation of natural ownership intersects with Bentham's state-centric view of property as a regulated artefact. Colonial administrators often considered communal landholding as illogical or inefficient, thus inserting statutory frameworks that privileged individual titles.

The LUA itself was a response to these competing frameworks: by vesting land in the state while granting “rights of occupancy” to individuals and communities, it attempted to harmonize customary and statutory norms. It sought to preserve indigenous landholding through deemed customary occupancy, while integrating statutory instruments that legitimized both *corpus* law and customary practice.³³

Thus, Nigerian property law emerges at the intersection of moral theory (Locke), state authority (Bentham), traditional practice, and administrative necessity—a layered dynamic that continues to shape property reform and jurisprudence.

2.1.3 Importance of Proprietary Rights in Land: Theoretical Justifications

³² J. Bentham, *An Introduction to the Principles of Morals and Legislation* (Oxford University Press 1907) 46.

³³ A. Ilori and A.K. Adebayo, “Customary Land Tenure System and the Land Use Act: A Comparative Analysis” (2019) 1 *International Review of Law and Jurisprudence* 92.

Proprietary rights in land serve crucial socio-economic and legal functions. First, they provide security of tenure — the assurance that the holder's rights will be recognized, protected, and enforceable. This security fosters confidence in long-term investments, as landholders are assured their improvements will not be seized arbitrarily. Economists term this the “security-investment-growth nexus”.³⁴ In Nigeria, issuance of a Certificate of Occupancy under the LUA furnishes this assurance to both urban and rural holders.³⁵

Second, proprietary rights facilitate active land markets. Transferability, enforceability, and officially recorded interests reduce transaction costs and risks. Land becomes liquid, usable as collateral — for mortgages, leases, or sale, stimulating real estate development, commerce, and agricultural productivity. Without such legal clarity, interest rates tend to be high due to uncertainty, and prospective investors remain cautious.³⁶

Third, proprietary rights help to exclude others, essential for efficient economic use. If multiple parties could claim *de facto* occupation without recourse, land development would be chaotic, underutilized, or contested. In Nigeria, the LUA seeks to balance community practice with individual controls, yet enforcement often requires recourse to courts or state action.

Fourth, entrenched proprietary rights support political and social stability. Land ownership, especially secure title — limits socio-political grievances around evictions and forced relocation. Conversely, arbitrary land revocation without fair compensation fuels social unrest.³⁷ Thus, constitutional guarantees such as sections 43 – 44 of the 1999 CFRN alongside LUA provisions demand due process and compensation for compulsory acquisition.³⁸

³⁴ F.K.F. Byamugisha and N. Dubosse, “The Investment Case for Land Tenure Security in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Cost–Benefit Analysis” (2023) 14 *Journal of Benefit-Cost Analysis* 272–300. (Cambridge University Press April 2021)

³⁵ LUA, s. 9.

³⁶ F.K.F. Byamugisha and N. Dubosse, *Ibid.*

³⁷ F.K.F. Byamugisha and N. Dubosse, Note 34.

³⁸ LUA, s. 29.

Lastly, proprietary rights align with liberty and autonomy theories, because when individuals can shape and control land, they exercise freedom of development and self-determination. Modern liberal theories argue that property is foundational to individual liberty.³⁹

In sum, proprietary rights in land are theoretically justified on grounds of economic efficiency, social justice, political stability, and personal liberty, underpinned by philosophical and legal rationales. In Nigeria, while the LUA structure aims to institutionalize these functions, practical challenges, such as delays in issuing Certificates of Occupancy, favoritism in issuance/revocation of Certificates of Occupancy and inconsistency in compensation, demonstrate the importance of refining the Act to truly deliver on these theoretical promises.

2.1.4 Distinction Between Proprietary Rights and Possessory Rights

Understanding the distinction between proprietary rights and possessory rights is fundamental to land law. Proprietary rights are legal titles to lands or interests therein — rights enforceable against all the world. They encompass a bundle of rights, including exclusion, transfer, inheritance, and enforcement in court.⁴⁰

Conversely, possessory rights refer to actual physical control or occupation (possession), supported by *animus possidendi* (intention to possess), but not necessarily backed by legal title.

Possession can be lawful (e.g., a tenant with valid title) or wrongful (e.g., a squatter).⁴¹

In Nigerian legal tradition, possessory rights may arise under customary tenure, where communities or individuals occupy land communally without state-recognized title. In such cases, the community may exercise populist, quasi-proprietary control recognized under customary norms, yet absent of statutory enforceability outside local customs.⁴²

³⁹ H. Dagan, *A Liberal Theory of Property* (Cambridge University Press April 2021) 24.

⁴⁰ I.O. Smith, Note 24.

⁴¹ See *Udeze v. Chidebe* (1990) 1 NWLR (Pt. 125) 141 at 162.

⁴² B.M. Salawu, “Harnessing Customary Land Tenure for Sustainable Resource Management in Rural Nigeria” (2025) 11 *NIULJS* 1

Possession is legally powerful. The law usually protects the right to exclude trespassers under possessory possession—evident in cases like *Buraimoh v Bamgbose*.⁴³ Courts consider effective long-term occupation and improvements as evidence of proprietary entitlement, especially under doctrines such as adverse possession (though Nigeria strictly applies recognized title).

However, possessory rights while capable of evolving into proprietary rights, remain inferior until validated by legal title. Under the LUA, holders of land pre-dating 29 March 1978 were deemed to have statutory or customary rights of occupancy, translating possession into recognized proprietary interests. This remedial action protected existing possessors under customary tenure, granting them enforceable proprietary rights.⁴⁴

Nevertheless, legal conflict often arises where possessory rights overlap with proprietary rights — for instance, when someone occupies land under customary belief but lacks permission from communal landowners. Here, proprietary interest may prevail, though courts will weigh evidence of possession, improvement, and public interest.

A few illustrative points:

- A tenant in occupation under a valid lease holds a proprietary right, enforceable via contract and property law.
- A squatter may hold possessory rights temporarily, enforceable only against third parties (not the owner), and does not gain full proprietary rights without prescription or legalization.
- Under LUA, possessing pre-existing title leads to a deemed grant—possessory becomes proprietary through legal fiction.

⁴³ *Buraimoh v Bamgbose* (1988) LCN/2401(SC).

⁴⁴ B.M. Salawu, *Ibid*.

Therefore, the distinction is crucial: possession signifies control; proprietary rights signify ownership recognized by law. Notwithstanding potential overlap, the law upholds proprietary rights as superior — possession constitutes a subset and may support claims but cannot override clear title. The LUA mediates the transition from possession to propriety, attempting to harmonize traditional occupancy with legal clarity.

2.2 Proprietary Rights on Land Prior to the Promulgation of the Land Use Act

2.2.1 Customary Land Tenure Systems

Before the introduction of formal land legislation in Nigeria, land was predominantly governed by customary law. These customary tenure systems were unwritten and varied significantly across the numerous ethnic and tribal communities in Nigeria. Generally, land was regarded as a communal asset, held in trust by traditional authorities such as family heads, village chiefs, or community elders, for the benefit of present and future generations. Ownership was rarely individualistic in the Western legal sense. Instead, individuals were granted usufructuary rights — the right to use and benefit from land but not the right to alienate or dispose of it permanently without the consent of the community or family.⁴⁵

Customary land tenure facilitated a strong sense of social cohesion and economic interdependence within communities. It ensured that land remained within the lineage or family and was used to support subsistence farming and communal living. However, the absence of formal documentation often led to conflicts, especially in urbanizing areas where land values appreciated significantly. This system proved inadequate in accommodating complex land transactions, investments, and infrastructural development. Customary rights were also subject

⁴⁵ M.I.O. Nwogu, “Ownership and Possession of Land under the Nigerian Customary Land Tenure System: A Legal Appraisal” (2023) 19(2) *Unizik Law Journal* 1-12.

to the discretionary powers of traditional leaders, sometimes leading to abuses and discriminatory practices against women and strangers.⁴⁶

Despite its limitations, the Nigerian legal system still recognizes customary land rights. In the case of *Amodu Tijani v Secretary, Southern Nigeria*,⁴⁷ the Privy Council held that customary land tenure should be respected and that native landholding rights constitute an interest recognized by law. Similarly, in *Oyewumi v Ogunesan*,⁴⁸ the court upheld the validity of customary inheritance rules, thereby confirming the legal force of customary tenure.

Nevertheless, the promulgation of the LUA in 1978 aimed to unify land tenure systems by vesting all land in the state governor, thereby subordinating customary systems to statutory control. *Section 1 of the LUA* vests all land in each state in the governor, to be held in trust for the people, and *Section 2* preserves customary rights only to the extent that they do not conflict with the Act. As such, while customary rights are still recognized, they are increasingly subject to statutory regulation.

2.2.2 Freehold and Leasehold Under Received English Law

The introduction of received English law into Nigeria's legal system during colonial rule brought with it the doctrine of estates in land, namely freehold and leasehold interests. Freehold conferred absolute ownership in perpetuity, while leasehold granted possession and use of land for a defined term, subject to the terms and conditions of a lease agreement. These concepts were embedded in land instruments introduced by colonial authorities and subsequently codified through various statutes and judicial decisions.⁴⁹

Under English common law, freehold ownership implied that the owner had both legal and equitable rights over the land, including the right to alienate, develop, or bequeath it. In contrast, leaseholders possessed only a temporary right to occupy the land, usually with a duty

⁴⁶ M.I.O. Nwogu, Note 45.

⁴⁷ *Amodu Tijani v Secretary, Southern Nigeria* (1921) AC 399.

⁴⁸ *Oyewumi v Ogunesan* (1990) 3 NWLR (Pt. 137) 182.

⁴⁹ I.O. Smith, Note 24, 141-160.

to pay rent. This framework, while providing clarity and predictability, was alien to indigenous communities where land was communally owned and individually held only for specific purposes.⁵⁰

The colonial authorities attempted to harmonize these systems through legislative enactments. *The Crown Lands Ordinance of 1902*⁵¹ and later the *Land and Native Rights Ordinance of 1916*⁵² formalized the allocation of land under English legal principles, thereby marginalizing customary systems. This approach often resulted in the expropriation of communal lands for public purposes without adequate consultation or compensation.

The courts also played a role in validating received English land tenure systems. In *Savannah Bank v Ajilo*,⁵³ the Supreme Court emphasized the necessity of aligning land transactions with statutory provisions, illustrating the legal supremacy of formalized interests over informal customary claims.

However, the LUA marked a significant departure from these doctrines. It abolished the distinction between freehold and leasehold estates and instead introduced the statutory and customary rights of occupancy. *Section 34* of the LUA converted existing freehold interests into statutory rights of occupancy, thus centralizing control of land in the hands of the governor.

2.2.3 Colonial and Pre-Independence Land Administration

Colonial and pre-independence land administration in Nigeria was characterized by a deliberate effort to centralize land control and harmonize tenure systems for the benefit of colonial governance and economic exploitation. The British colonial administration introduced

⁵⁰ I.O. Smith, Note 24, 141-160.

⁵¹ Crown Lands Ordinance of 1902.

⁵² Land and Native Rights Ordinance of 1916.

⁵³ *Savannah Bank v Ajilo* (1989) 1 NWLR (Pt. 97) 305.

ordinances aimed at formalizing land acquisition and usage, often at the expense of indigenous land rights.⁵⁴

The *Crown Lands Ordinance of 1902* allowed the colonial government to claim ownership of land that was not visibly occupied, thereby facilitating European settlement and administrative expansion. This was followed by the *Land and Native Rights Ordinance of 1916*, which extended this claim to the Northern Protectorate by vesting all native lands in the Governor for the benefit of the natives. These ordinances laid the foundation for subsequent expropriations and alienations of communal lands.⁵⁵

In the South, the colonial authorities faced resistance due to existing and entrenched customary systems. *The Native Lands Acquisition Ordinance of 1917*⁵⁶ was enacted to regulate the acquisition of land by non-natives and companies. It required the approval of the colonial administration before such transactions could be valid. This legislative framework initially was designed to prevent exploitation, but in practice, it also stifled land development by creating bureaucratic bottlenecks.

The colonial land policy reinforced a dual land tenure system, with statutory control in urban centers and customary tenure prevailing in rural areas. This dualism persisted into the post-independence era, creating inconsistencies in land administration. By independence in 1960, Nigeria had inherited a fragmented and confusing land tenure structure that necessitated reform.⁵⁷

⁵⁴ O.F. Kasim and SB Agbola, Note 20.

⁵⁵ O.F. Kasim and SB Agbola, Note 20.

⁵⁶ Native Lands Acquisition Ordinance of 1917

⁵⁷ O.F. Kasim and SB Agbola, *ibid.*

The LUA was introduced to address these challenges by unifying landholding under a single statutory framework. As noted in *Nkwocha v Governor of Anambra State*,⁵⁸ the Supreme Court affirmed that the LUA was intended to ensure uniformity and prevent the abuse of landholding powers across Nigeria.

2.2.4 Challenges of Multiplicity of Landholding Systems

The co-existence of multiple landholding systems in Nigeria has historically created significant legal, administrative, and social challenges. The fragmentation arises primarily from the interplay between customary and statutory tenure systems, each operating under different legal principles, and often overlapping in their claims to the same parcel of land.⁵⁹

Customary systems rely on oral traditions and communal recognition, while statutory systems depend on formal documentation and registration. The lack of harmonization between these two systems often results in disputes over land ownership, boundaries, and inheritance. In urban areas especially, the rapid commercialization of land has brought customary claims into direct conflict with statutory requirements for land title registration and documentation.

Courts have frequently been called upon to resolve these disputes. In *Ogunleye v Oni*,⁶⁰ the Supreme Court recognized that a person with a statutory right of occupancy could have superior title to someone with a customary right, particularly where the former has complied with formal registration requirements. However, in *Amodu Tijani v Secretary, Southern Nigeria*,⁶¹ the Privy Council emphasized that customary rights must not be arbitrarily extinguished. This legal uncertainty has had practical consequences. Investors are often reluctant to engage in transactions where land titles are unclear or undefined, and banks are unwilling to accept such

⁵⁸ *Nkwocha v Governor of Anambra State* (1984) 6 SC 362.

⁵⁹ O. Lewis, "Resolving the Problem of Land Ownership in Nigeria" (2025) 33(1) *African Journal of International and Comparative Law* 142-165.

⁶⁰ *Ogunleye v Oni* (1990) 2 NWLR (Pt. 135) 745.

⁶¹ Note 47.

land as collateral. Additionally, the administrative burden of resolving disputes and managing land allocations strains government institutions.

The LUA attempted to resolve these problems by vesting all land in the state governor and formalizing occupancy rights. However, implementation has been inconsistent, and many communities continue to assert customary claims without recourse to formal procedures. This calls for a more integrated approach to land administration that respects customary practices while promoting legal certainty and economic development.

2.3 Proprietary Right: An Unjust Enrichment or Not?

2.3.1 Legal Theories on Unjust Enrichment

Unjust enrichment, as a legal doctrine, concerns the restoration of benefits unjustly retained by one party at the expense of another. Traditionally grounded in contract and restitution law, the concept is increasingly relevant in property law, particularly where proprietary rights confer unequal advantages.⁶² The classical formulation, as seen in *Fibrosa Spolka Akcyjna v Fairbairn Lawson Combe Barbour Ltd*,⁶³ holds that enrichment must be unjust, and there must be no valid legal basis (such as contract or gift) for the enrichment to stand.

In land law, unjust enrichment arises when legal or institutional frameworks permit individuals or entities to acquire, hold, or benefit from land resources without proportional input, investment, or contribution. For instance, when large tracts of land are allocated to politically connected individuals at subsidized rates under the guise of statutory grants, the resultant proprietary interest may be viewed as unjust enrichment at the expense of the general public.⁶⁴

⁶² Lusina Ho, “Unjust Enrichment and Equity” in *Research Handbook on Unjust Enrichment and Restitution* (Edward Elgar Publishing, 2020) 123-144.

⁶³ *Fibrosa Spolka Akcyjna v Fairbairn Lawson Combe Barbour Ltd* [1943] AC 32.

⁶⁴ T.B. Nadler and P. Evans-Jones (eds), *Unjustified Enrichment: Key Issues in Comparative Perspective* (Cambridge University Press, 2002) 71.

In Nigeria, the LUA vested all land in each state in the Governor, ostensibly to ensure equitable redistribution. However, this has often led to administrative abuses where land allocations favor elites, leaving many (including the middle class or average) landless. The courts have generally refrained from applying the doctrine of unjust enrichment directly in land matters, but scholars argue that such instances violate the equitable maxim *nemo debet locupletari ex aliena jactura* (no one should be enriched by another's loss).⁶⁵

Critics contend that the LUA has enabled unjust patterns of enrichment. For instance, in *Abiodun v Minister of Lands and Housing*,⁶⁶ the court held that statutory rights of occupancy granted under the LUA must follow due process, but the case highlighted concerns about arbitrary allocations to powerful interests. In such situations, the notion of unjust enrichment challenges the moral and legal legitimacy of proprietary rights granted through corrupt or exclusionary means.

Thus, the principle of unjust enrichment forces a reevaluation of how land law operates in Nigeria, particularly in terms of who benefits from statutory land allocations and who bears the cost of displacement or exclusion. It calls for reforms that align legal entitlements with principles of fairness, justice, and economic inclusion.

2.3.2 Analysis of Proprietary Interests in a Developing Economy

In developing economies like Nigeria, proprietary interests in land reflect deep-rooted social and economic disparities. Land is a central asset in these societies, not only for shelter and agriculture but also for political power and economic leverage. However, rather than fostering broad-based development, proprietary rights often consolidate wealth and privilege among the elite.

⁶⁵ B. Ibhawoh, *Human Rights in Africa: The Politics of Land Reform* (Cambridge University Press 2014) 14.

⁶⁶ *Abiodun v Minister of Lands and Housing* (2005) 11 NWLR (Pt. 935) 1.

This disparity is largely a function of how land is allocated and managed. The LUA, though intended to democratize land ownership and curb speculative acquisition, has been critiqued for enabling state capture of land resources. In practice, state governors exercise near-absolute discretion in granting rights of occupancy, often favoring well-connected individuals and corporations.⁶⁷ This undermines the original intent of the LUA, replacing the chaos of multiple tenure systems with a centralized system ripe for abuse.

A vivid illustration of this is the controversial allocation of land in Abuja, where multiple rights of occupancy were granted over the same parcel of land, leading to prolonged litigation and displacement of original occupants *Osho v Foreign Finance Corporation*.⁶⁸ These cases underscore the fragility of proprietary rights for the average Nigerian and the precarious nature of land tenure security in urban areas.

Proprietary rights, when concentrated in the hands of a few, create barriers to entry for others, especially the urban poor. Informal settlements, lacking legal title, are routinely demolished, sometimes without adequate notice or compensation, highlighting the exploitative potential of unchecked proprietary rights. The principle of security of tenure — central to human development, is thus compromised in many Nigerian cities.⁶⁹

This scenario demands a rethink of proprietary frameworks to ensure they serve developmental goals rather than entrench inequality. Ensuring transparency in land allocation, regularizing informal tenure systems, and empowering local communities with secure rights can help address the distortions in landholding. Ultimately, proprietary rights must be situated within the broader framework of distributive justice and inclusive development.

2.3.3 Equity and Fairness in Property Allocation

⁶⁷ K.H. Babalola and SA Hull, Note 18.

⁶⁸ *Osho v Foreign Finance Corporation* (1991) 4 NWLR (Pt. 184) 157.

⁶⁹ UN-Habitat, *The State of African Cities 2015: Urbanization and Economic Growth* (United Nations Human Settlements Programme 2015).

Equity and fairness are cardinal principles in the administration of property rights, especially in a constitutional democracy. The equitable allocation of land ensures that no group or class is unduly favored in a manner that disadvantages others. In Nigeria, however, the promise of equity under the LUA has often been undermined by administrative practices and systemic bias.

Section 44 of the 1999 CFRN guarantees the right to property and stipulates that no property shall be compulsorily acquired without prompt payment of compensation. Nevertheless, compulsory acquisition has often been carried out in a manner that violates procedural fairness. For instance, in *Osho v Foreign Finance Corporation* (supra), the Supreme Court emphasized that acquisition of land without adequate compensation or legal procedure constitutes a breach of fundamental rights.

The discretionary powers vested in state governors under the LUA are significant contributors to inequity. Although *Section 5 of the LUA* permits the grant of statutory rights of occupancy, the lack of clear, enforceable criteria for allocation creates room for favoritism. Studies have shown that political patronage heavily influences land allocations, particularly in urban centers.⁷⁰ This denies land access to the economically disadvantaged and erodes public trust in property systems.

Furthermore, the principle of fairness demands adequate compensation for land acquired in the public interest. Yet, delays in compensation, poor valuation practices, and lack of access to legal remedies often leave dispossessed persons worse off. This undermines the ethical foundation of proprietary rights and contradicts the spirit of social justice embodied in Nigeria's constitutional and legal order.⁷¹

⁷⁰ I. Nwosu, "Governance, Land and Equity in Nigeria's Urban Development" (2016) 7(3) *Nigerian Journal of Sustainable Development Law and Policy* 112

⁷¹ T.T. Oladokun, "Improving Land Governance in Nigeria: The Case of Compulsory Acquisition and Compensation Practice" (2023) 17 *Journal of Civil Engineering and Architecture* 251-257.

Promoting fairness in land allocation requires legal reforms to check executive discretion, establish independent land commissions, and ensure judicial oversight. Additionally, mechanisms like participatory land-use planning, referendum and transparent public registers can enhance equity in property systems.

2.3.4 The Role of Access and Exclusion in Economic Empowerment

Access to land is a critical determinant of economic empowerment. In agrarian and rapidly urbanizing economies like Nigeria, land serves as a means of livelihood, collateral for credit, and a source of social identity. Conversely, exclusion from landholding reproduces cycles of impoverishment, insecurity, and social disempowerment.

The LUA was envisioned as a tool for ensuring equitable access by vesting land in the state and controlling its use for the common good. However, in practice, access has remained skewed. The cumbersome process of obtaining a certificate of occupancy, for example, excludes the poor and illiterate from formal land markets. In many cases, land acquisition is limited to those with the means to navigate administrative bottlenecks or leverage political connections.⁷²

Women and rural dwellers are particularly vulnerable. Despite constitutional guarantees of non-discrimination, cultural practices and institutional bias limit women's access to land. Moreover, displaced communities often face prolonged marginalization without meaningful integration into urban economic systems. The exclusionary nature of land governance structures thus hampers inclusive growth.⁷³

This dynamic is exacerbated by land speculation and commodification. Private developers often acquire vast swathes of land, displacing communities and driving up prices, further limiting access for low-income groups. The Abuja Urban Renewal Scheme provides a case in

⁷² B. Ibhawoh, Note 66.

⁷³ T. Ajala, "Gender Discrimination in Land Ownership and the Alleviation of Women's Poverty in Nigeria: A Call for New Equities" (2017) 17(1) *International Journal of Discrimination and the Law* 51-66.

point, where resettlement promises went unfulfilled and economic disenfranchisement ensued.⁷⁴

Land reforms must prioritize inclusive policies that expand access to marginalized groups. Community titling, simplified documentation, legal aid for land disputes, and state-subsidized housing schemes can mitigate exclusion. Empowering individuals through secure land rights catalyzes investment, productivity, and long-term economic upliftment.

2.4 Significant Revocation Theories Affecting the Proprietary Rights of Individuals to Land

2.4.1 Eminent Domain and Compulsory Acquisition

Eminent domain, also referred to as compulsory acquisition in Nigerian legal parlance, is the power vested in the state to expropriate private land for public use upon payment of compensation. This power is codified under *Section 28 of the LUA 1978*, and further reinforced by *Section 44(1) of the CFRN 1999 (as amended 2011)*. While this legal framework appears balanced on the surface—recognizing both the authority of the state and the rights of landowners—its implementation has sparked intense controversy due to frequent procedural abuses, under-compensation/inadequate compensation, and disregard for due process.

In principle, the doctrine of eminent domain aims to ensure that land required for public purposes such as infrastructure, education, and health facilities can be obtained by the government without being hindered by individual ownership claims. However, the reality in Nigeria has often deviated from this objective. Numerous instances have emerged where land is acquired without adherence to the procedural safeguards stipulated under the LUA.⁷⁵ For instance, under *Section 28(6) of the LUA*, the Governor is mandated to notify the holder of the right of occupancy in writing and to pay compensation promptly. Yet, in practice, such notices

⁷⁴ Amnesty International, *Nigeria: Forced Evictions in Abuja Make Thousands Homeless* (Amnesty International, 2008).

⁷⁵ T.T. Oladokun, Note 71.

are sometimes vague, delayed, or entirely omitted, leaving affected individuals without recourse.

In *Osho v Foreign Finance Corporation*,⁷⁶ the Supreme Court emphasized that the acquisition of land without proper notice and due process amounts to a violation of constitutional rights. The court reiterated that the power of compulsory acquisition must be exercised judiciously, not arbitrarily, and must be guided by both statutory and constitutional provisions. Unfortunately, reports abound of state governors revoking land rights for reasons not linked to public interest, sometimes redistributing such lands to political allies or private developers.

The inadequacy of compensation is another thorny issue. The LUA only mandates compensation for unexhausted improvements,⁷⁷ not for the land itself, as ownership is deemed to rest with the state. This provision severely limits the economic rights of landholders. Moreover, the assessment of compensation is often unscientific, with delayed or partial payments. This discourages investment in land development and diminishes public trust in land governance mechanisms.⁷⁸

In sum, while the doctrine of eminent domain serves an essential public function, its abuse in Nigeria under the cover of LUA provisions has eroded confidence in land rights. The unchecked powers of state executives in exercising revocations undermine the principle of security of tenure and raise urgent calls for legal reform to reinforce accountability and protect private proprietary rights.

2.4.2 Public Purpose Doctrine and Compensation Mechanisms

The doctrine of "public purpose" serves as a legal threshold that must be met before the state can legitimately expropriate land. This requirement is enshrined in Section 44(1)(a) *CFRN 1999*, which provides that no movable or immovable property shall be compulsorily taken

⁷⁶ Note 68.

⁷⁷ LUA, s. 29.

⁷⁸ T.T. Oladokun, Note 71.

possession of or acquired except for public purposes and with prompt payment of compensation. The LUA also reflects this standard in Section 28(2), which allows revocation of rights of occupancy for overriding public interest. However, the ambiguity surrounding what qualifies as "public purpose" has led to widespread abuse and judicial controversy.

Historically, public purpose included infrastructure development, public schools, hospitals, and roads. However, in practice, this has extended to commercial real estate, shopping complexes, and even private housing estates under the pretext of economic development.⁷⁹ This expansive interpretation has undermined the constitutional safeguards meant to protect private landowners. In *Olatunji v Military Governor of Oyo State*,⁸⁰ the court held that a purported acquisition for public purpose that turns out to benefit private interests is unlawful and unconstitutional.

Another concern is the loophole in the compensation mechanism. Under Section 29 LUA, compensation is payable only for the value of unexhausted improvements on the land, not for the land itself, since the law vests all land in the Governor as trustee. This legal fiction means that while landowners lose access and use rights, they are only compensated for structures or crops, leaving them economically disadvantaged. This provision has been criticized for being inequitable and at variance with global best practices, which recognize full land value compensation.⁸¹

Furthermore, compensation mechanisms are often mired in bureaucratic inefficiency, delays, and under-assessment. In *Goldmark Nigeria Ltd v Ibafo Co. Ltd*,⁸² the Supreme Court acknowledged the right of affected individuals to adequate and timely compensation and

⁷⁹ S Nwatu and C Ajibo, "Compulsory Acquisition of Land (Private Property) in Nigeria: Prioritizing Public Interest over Private Interest" (2021) 16 *The Nigerian Juridical Review* 275-289.

⁸⁰ *Olatunji v Military Governor of Oyo State* (1994) 4 NWLR (Pt 336) 1.

⁸¹ S Nwatu and C Ajibo, *Ibid.*

⁸² *Goldmark Nigeria Ltd v Ibafo Co. Ltd* (2012) LPELR-9340(SC).

declared any acquisition invalid where such rights are violated. However, enforcement remains a significant hurdle till date.

The courts have occasionally stepped in to interpret the scope of public purpose and the adequacy of compensation. Yet, such judicial interventions have not been sufficient to deter misuse. Critics argue for clearer statutory guidelines and judicial oversight to ensure public purpose is narrowly construed and that compensation is both prompt and just.⁸³

In sum, the doctrine of public purpose is vital to justify land acquisition by the state. However, its current interpretation and compensation practice in Nigeria are problematic. Legal reforms are necessary to define "public purpose" narrowly, enhance transparency, and make compensation mechanisms more equitable and efficient.

2.4.3 Judicial Interpretation of Revocation Powers

Judicial interpretation plays a crucial role in regulating and restraining the exercise of land revocation powers under the LUA. While Section 28 of the LUA confers upon the Governor the power to revoke a right of occupancy for overriding public interest, Nigerian courts have consistently held that this power must be exercised in strict compliance with the law and procedural fairness.

In *Olatunji v Military Governor of Oyo State*,⁸⁴ the Court of Appeal emphasized that even when land is required for public use, revocation must be carried out in accordance with due process. In this case, the court nullified a revocation that was not preceded by adequate notice and fair hearing. This case set a critical precedent, reinforcing that statutory compliance is not merely procedural but foundational to the validity of any revocation.

Similarly, in *Attorney General, Lagos State v Ajayi*,⁸⁵ the Supreme Court held that a revocation of land rights under the LUA that is not for a genuine public purpose, or one that fails to satisfy

⁸³ S Nwatu and C Ajibo, *Ibid.*

⁸⁴ Note 80.

⁸⁵ *A-G Lagos State v Ajayi* (2000) 12 NWLR (Pt 682) 509.

compensation obligations, is liable to be struck down. The court warned against the arbitrary use of state power under the guise of public purpose, particularly when the real intent is to transfer land to third parties for commercial gain.

The judiciary has also interpreted the compensation clause under Section 29 LUA narrowly, often to the disadvantage of landowners. While courts recognize that compensation is constitutionally required, the limitation to unexhausted improvements (as opposed to land value) has been upheld, although with judicial concern. In *Ijewere v Igbinovia*,⁸⁶ the court acknowledged the unjust outcome of paying compensation only for surface developments, but still affirmed that such is the legislative intent of the LUA.

These cases illustrate a judicial balancing act between respecting legislative authority and safeguarding individual rights. However, the courts are often limited by the statutory wording of the LUA, which vests broad discretion in the Governor. As such, although judicial interpretation has occasionally checked executive overreach, more robust statutory reform is needed to strengthen protections against arbitrary revocation.

2.4.4 Case Law Review: Trends and Impacts on Proprietary Rights

An evolving trend in Nigerian jurisprudence reveals growing judicial unease with the manner in which land revocation powers are exercised. Over the years, courts have demonstrated a willingness to scrutinize executive actions, especially where they affect proprietary rights under questionable interpretations of public interest.

In *Nkwocha v Governor of Anambra State*,⁸⁷ the Supreme Court upheld the constitutionality of the LUA but cautioned that its implementation must not infringe upon the rights of citizens

⁸⁶ *Ijewere v Igbinovia* (1992) 2 NWLR (Pt 226) 578.

⁸⁷ Note 58.

arbitrarily. This foundational case has been cited in subsequent decisions where revocations failed to comply with due process.

In *Bello v Diocesan Synod of Lagos*,⁸⁸ although pre-LUA, the court stressed that even under public acquisition laws, there must be strict adherence to procedural rules, including notice and fair hearing. The doctrine has been carried into post-LUA jurisprudence, reinforcing the importance of procedural safeguards.

Another key case is *Adole v Gwar*,⁸⁹ where the Supreme Court reiterated that the Governor's revocation powers must be exercised strictly within the confines of Sections 28 and 29 LUA. Where land is revoked outside of these confines or compensation is not paid, the acquisition will be nullified.

This jurisprudence indicates a growing judicial resolve to protect land rights, but systemic enforcement problems persist. For example, despite numerous favorable judgments, state agencies sometimes ignore court orders or delay implementation. Moreover, courts are constrained by the text of the LUA, which still centralizes ownership in the Governor and limits compensation.

Thus, while case law reflects incremental progress in protecting proprietary rights, legislative and institutional reforms are required to give full effect to judicial pronouncements. The courts alone cannot cure the structural deficiencies of the LUA, particularly regarding compensation and the scope of revocation powers.

2.5 The High Value System of Land and Its Scarcity in Present Times

2.5.1 The Economic and Social Importance of Land

⁸⁸ *Bello v Diocesan Synod of Lagos* (1973) 3 SC 131.

⁸⁹ *Adole v Gwar* (2008) 11 NWLR (Pt 1099) 562.

Land holds immense economic and social significance in Nigeria, serving as a critical asset for wealth creation, socio-political influence, and economic development. In agrarian societies, land is the primary source of livelihood, facilitating agricultural activities and rural sustenance. In urban contexts, land is central to industrial and residential development, making it a key component of national productivity and economic diversification. Thus, ownership and control of land often translate into economic security and social capital.⁹⁰

In Nigerian law, the importance of land is underscored by the central role it plays in legislative frameworks such as the LUA. Section 1 of the LUA vests all land in each state in the Governor, to be held in trust for the people. This public trusteeship model was intended to democratize land access and curb excessive land monopolies. However, the social function of land has not been fully realized due to continued elite capture and bureaucratic inefficiencies.

Historically, the accumulation of land in the hands of a few individuals or families has created entrenched socio-economic disparities. This is particularly visible in regions where ancestral claims or customary tenure systems dominate. As a result, land is not just an economic resource but also a marker of identity, tradition, and power. For instance, under customary law, land symbolizes communal heritage and continuity, often making alienation or commodification a sensitive issue.⁹¹

Judicial pronouncements have recognized the primacy of land to socio-economic rights. In *Nkwocha v Governor of Anambra State*,⁹² the Supreme Court described the LUA as a statute of social engineering aimed at reforming land tenure and ensuring equitable access. Despite

⁹⁰ R.A. Adeogun and S.O. Oni, "Ownership and Compulsory Acquisition under Customary Land Tenure in South-West Nigeria: A Legal and Socio-Cultural Analysis" (2025) 8 *African Journal of Law, Political Research and Administration* 1–12.

⁹¹ I. Adewumi and F. Olokesusi, "Land Reform in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects" (2011) *NISER Monograph Series, Ibadan* 1-9.

⁹² Note 58.

this intention, the actual operation of the LUA has often fallen short due to inconsistent implementation and lack of clear access frameworks.

In essence, land remains a linchpin for economic empowerment, poverty alleviation, and socio-political inclusion. The inability to secure land tenure undermines these objectives and fuels social unrest. For meaningful development, there is a need for a land regime that recognizes both the economic utility and socio-cultural value of land, ensuring equitable distribution and tenure security for all Nigerians.

2.5.2 Urbanization and the Pressure on Land Resources

Nigeria's rapid urbanization presents a critical challenge to land resource management. With an urban population growing at an estimated 4.3% annually, cities like Lagos, Abuja, and Port Harcourt are witnessing an unprecedented surge in demand for land.⁹³ This urban expansion exerts enormous pressure on available land, creating a mismatch between demand and supply and leading to a variety of socio-economic problems including housing deficits, slum proliferation, and land speculation.

Urban land scarcity in Nigeria is worsened by the centralization provisions of the LUA, which vests control of land in state governors. Section 5 of the LUA empowers the governor to grant statutory rights of occupancy, but the process is often opaque and influenced by political and bureaucratic patronage. This has led to distortions in the urban land market and has marginalized the urban poor, many of whom resort to informal settlements or illegal occupations.

In *Osho v Foreign Finance Corp.*,⁹⁴ the court acknowledged that statutory rights under the LUA are subject to the discretion of the governor, reflecting the significant administrative

⁹³ UN-Habitat, *The State of African Cities 2020: Managing Urban Land* (United Nations 2020).

⁹⁴ Note 68.

control that can hinder land access. Furthermore, inadequate urban planning and outdated cadastral systems result in overlapping land claims and tenure insecurity, complicating the land acquisition process.

The consequences of poor urban land governance are manifest in the growth of unregulated settlements, many of which lack basic infrastructure such as roads, water, and sanitation. These settlements, commonly termed “urban slums,” have become home to millions of Nigerians. For example, in Makoko, Lagos, residents have long faced eviction threats due to lack of formal land titles despite decades of occupation.⁹⁵

Moreover, public infrastructure projects such as highways and airports often necessitate large-scale land acquisition, leading to disputes and evictions. While Section 28 of the LUA permits compulsory acquisition for public purposes, its implementation often disregards fair procedures and adequate compensation, thus exacerbating urban tensions.

Overall, unless there is an overhaul of the current land governance system to improve transparency, decentralize authority, and incorporate participatory urban planning, the pressure on urban land will continue to mount, undermining inclusive and sustainable city development.

2.5.3 Agricultural and Industrial Demands

Land is indispensable to Nigeria’s aspirations for agricultural rejuvenation and industrial development. With over 70% of the population engaged in agriculture, land is the primary means of production for millions of Nigerians. It provides the foundation for food security, raw materials for industries, and employment opportunities across rural and peri-urban

⁹⁵ A.O. Agboola and A.R. Amidu, “Rethinking Effective Urban Land Governance in Sub-Saharan Africa: Moving Towards a Transcendental Critical Realist Approach” (2023) 34 *Urban Forum* 253–269.

communities. However, access to arable land is increasingly hampered by legal, institutional, and infrastructural bottlenecks.⁹⁶

The LUA, despite its intention to harmonize land tenure and enhance access, has inadvertently constrained the agricultural sector. The requirement for governor's consent under Section 22 before alienation creates delays that hinder large-scale agricultural investments/agronomy. Investors and local farmers alike struggle with insecure tenure, discouraging long-term productivity and environmental stewardship.

Industrial land needs are similarly affected. Special economic zones, industrial parks, and manufacturing hubs require extensive land for infrastructure, logistics, and processing. However, acquisition procedures under the LUA are cumbersome and often involve opaque processes that delay implementation and increase costs. This challenge is particularly acute for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) that lack political or financial capital to navigate the bureaucracy.

Conflicts between industrial use and agriculture are also growing. Large-scale land acquisitions for agribusiness or extractive industries often displace smallholder farmers, sometimes without adequate compensation or resettlement, thus deepening rural poverty. Cases such as *Shell Petroleum Dev. Co. v. Isaiah*⁹⁷ reveal how land-related industrial activity can cause community dispossession and environmental degradation.

Additionally, poor land documentation and conflicting claims often between customary and statutory holders, undermines industrial certainty and inflate transactional risks. A lack of nationwide cadastral data or a uniform digital land registry makes it difficult to ascertain land status, ownership history, or encumbrances, thereby stifling economic planning.

⁹⁶ O.L. Makinde, O.O. Alawode and R.A. Olaoye, "Legal Issues in Land Acquisition for Agricultural Production in Nigeria" (2024) 8(2) *American Journal of Agricultural Science, Engineering, and Technology* 1–9.

⁹⁷ *Shell Petroleum Dev. Co. v. Isaiah* (2001) FWLR (Pt. 56) 608.

To unlock the full potential of land for agriculture and industry, Nigeria needs a reformed proprietary rights regime that streamlines acquisition, secures tenure, and protects community rights. Clear legal frameworks, digitization of land records, and improved dispute resolution mechanisms are essential to fostering investor confidence and enhancing national development.

2.5.4 Speculation, Land Grabbing, and Market Distortions

Speculation and land grabbing have emerged as significant threats to equitable land distribution in Nigeria. Speculative investment driven by expectations of rising land values leads to hoarding, underutilization, and inflated land prices. Land is increasingly treated as a financial asset rather than a productive resource, especially in urban areas, where real estate speculation is rampant.⁹⁸

Politically connected individuals often exploit their influence to acquire large tracts of land, sometimes under the guise of public purpose acquisitions, only to later convert them for private gain. This form of elite capture undermines the LUA's intent, as land granted under public trust is diverted to serve private interests. The lack of transparency and accountability in land allocation facilitates this abuse.⁹⁹

Land grabbing also affects rural communities, where local elites or corporations acquire customary land without proper consultation or compensation. This often results in displacement, loss of livelihood, and community disintegration. In *Abioye v Yakubu*,¹⁰⁰ the court affirmed the recognition of customary land rights, yet such rights remain vulnerable to expropriation under weak enforcement mechanisms.

The speculative market distorts land values, making it unaffordable for low- and middle-income earners. It also leads to idle land, as owners wait for value appreciation rather than

⁹⁸ Joseph Oyedeji, "Assessment of Land Speculator's Operation for Land Accessibility in Nigeria" (2022) 10(1) *Baltic Journal of Real Estate Economics and Construction Management* 26–40

⁹⁹ Joseph Oyedeji, Note 98.

¹⁰⁰ *Abioye v Yakubu* [1991] 5 NWLR (Pt 190) 130.

develop the property. This contradicts the LUA's underlying philosophy of putting land to productive use and facilitating equitable access.

Furthermore, land speculation encourages informal settlements as displaced individuals seek alternative accommodation, leading to environmental degradation and unplanned urban sprawl. The failure of governments to tax idle land or enforce development conditions further exacerbates the issue.¹⁰¹

To counteract speculation and land grabbing, a comprehensive land reform strategy is required. This should include strict enforcement of land use conditions under Section 28 of the LUA, taxation of unused land, and a transparent land allocation process that prioritizes genuine need and public interest. Effective legal mechanisms must also be instituted to recognize and protect customary rights against arbitrary dispossession.

2.6 Conclusion

In sum, the historical and legal foundation of proprietary rights in Nigeria reveals a complex and layered evolution shaped by indigenous norms, colonial interventions, and post-colonial legal reforms. The transition from communal and family-based customary landholding to individualized proprietary claims under statutory law has not been seamless. The legal dichotomy between customary and statutory systems created ambiguity, which the LUA of 1978 sought to resolve. However, the Act itself has introduced a centralization model that, while attempting to ensure equitable access to land, has also raised serious concerns regarding the security of individual property rights and the abuse of governmental discretion.

This chapter has shown that proprietary rights in land are not merely legal entitlements but also socio-economic tools with the potential to empower or marginalize, depending on the structure of access, control, and enforcement. Issues such as unjust enrichment, lack of procedural fairness in compulsory acquisitions, speculative practices, and urbanization pressures

¹⁰¹ Joseph Oyedeji, *Ibid.*

underscore the continuing relevance of strong and clear proprietary protections. The high value and limited availability of land in Nigeria amplify these challenges. As this study progresses, it will critically examine how the LUA has shaped—and in some instances constrained—these rights, and what prospects exist for a more equitable land regime.

CHAPTER THREE

LAND USE ACT AND INDIVIDUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

3.0 Introduction

The LUA of 1978 marked a dramatic departure from the pluralistic and often conflicting land tenure systems that previously characterized Nigeria's land administration. By vesting all land in each state in the hands of the Governor to hold in trust for the people, the Act effectively restructured the concept of land ownership in Nigeria, redefining private proprietary rights and institutionalizing a statutory occupancy regime. Although enacted with the objective of simplifying land acquisition, promoting equitable distribution, and curbing land speculation and exploitation, the Act has continued to attract sustained scrutiny from legal scholars, property rights advocates, and development economists alike. This is largely because of the inherent tension it creates between individual rights and state control.

This chapter explores the implications of the LUA on private proprietary rights in Nigeria. It examines the new forms of interests created by the Act, including customary and statutory

rights of occupancy, the certificate of occupancy, and the legal status of licenses and permits. The chapter also analyses how the Act has altered the traditional doctrine of estates, imposed administrative barriers on land transactions, and expanded the Governor’s powers over revocation and alienation. The interaction between the Land Use Act and constitutional property guarantees is also critically assessed.

3.1 Other Forms of Rights Prevalent in the Land Use Act

3.1.1 Statutory Right of Occupancy

Under Section 5 of the LUA, the statutory right of occupancy (SRO) is granted by the Governor to individuals or bodies for land in urban areas. This right bestows exclusive possession and a legally transparent tenure framework compared to customary rights, laying the foundation for urban land development and secured transactions.

Section 5(1) grants land to applicants, while Section 5(2) provides that upon grant, all prior rights are extinguished—creating a single, transferable, and enforceable interest. The Supreme Court in *Akande v Kolere*¹⁰² acknowledged this extinguishment, emphasizing the singular nature of statutory occupancy.

This framework caters to urban planning, real estate development, and mortgage financing; a registered statutory right of occupancy (SRO) is a precondition for secured lending. However, the tenure remains derivative — the land is vested in the State Governor, not in fee simple by the grantee. This alignment places ultimate authority with the State, as seen in how revocation and alienation rights flow from statutory discretion rather than absolute ownership.

Despite its apparent strength, the SRO’s reliance on state discretion introduces vulnerability. Granting is subject to administrative approval and compliance with planning regulations;

¹⁰² *Akande v Kolere* (1966) NNLR 113.

alienation of land requires the Governor's consent under Section 22, and failure to obtain it renders a transfer void, as demonstrated in *Union Bank Plc v Ayodare*.¹⁰³

Moreover, while certification offers legal solidity, revocation remains possible if deemed in the public interest under Section 28. The requirement for fair compensation and strict procedural compliance is often neglected, resulting in high-profile litigation, such as *CSS Bookshops Ltd v. RTMCRS* and *Osho v Foreign Finance Corp*.¹⁰⁴

Thus, while the SRO structure improves the formal protection of land rights, it does not establish freehold ownership. It remains contingent upon ongoing state goodwill and procedural fairness, exacerbating long-term tenure uncertainty especially where bureaucratic inefficiencies or political interference exist.¹⁰⁵

3.1.2 Customary Right of Occupancy

The customary right of occupancy is one of two primary forms of land tenure recognized by the LUA, specifically under Section 6. Local Governments may grant such rights over rural or non-urban land areas, traditionally governed by customary law. Section 6(1)(a) empowers Local Councils to allocate land for agricultural, residential, or ancillary purposes on that basis, while Section 6(2) imposes limits (500 hectares for agriculture, 5,000 hectares for grazing), requiring Governor's consent for larger grants. Despite lawful statutory basis, these rights are deeply rooted in pre-colonial land practices, representing a hybrid of customary law and statutory regulation.

Under customary tenure, grantees enjoy a right to exclusive use and enjoyment of land, governed by local norms—often indefinite and inheritable. Section 36 of the LUA also provides that persons already in occupation for agricultural purposes at commencement are

¹⁰³ *Union Bank of Nigeria Plc & Another v Ayodare & Sons (Nig) Ltd* (SC. 375/2001) [2007] NGSC 148.

¹⁰⁴ *CSS Bookshops Ltd v Registered Trustees of Muslim Community in Rivers State* (2006) 4 SCNJ 310.

¹⁰⁵ AT Abayomi, "Analysing the Concept of Right of Occupancy under the Nigeria Land Use Act" (2022) 3 *Jus Corpus Law Journal* 1065.

deemed to hold a customary right of occupancy. This deemed grant safeguards continuous occupation, preserving evolved customary use rights.

However, these rights are often weak in documentation. Most grants are informal and lack formal survey or registration, leaving grantees vulnerable to encroachment or competing claims. The need for written consent in transactions—under Section 22, requiring Local Government approval—frequently goes unheeded due to lack of awareness or bureaucratic corruption. Cases such as *Union Bank v Ayodare*¹⁰⁶ illustrate nullification of transfers without due consent, reinforcing the statutory safeguards despite poor implementation.

Moreover, customary rights are revocable under Section 6(3), allowing Local Governments to reclaim land for public purposes—subject only to compensation for unexhausted improvements¹⁰⁷ and alternative allocation where land was used agriculturally.¹⁰⁸ In practice, however, such procedures are unevenly applied, and compensation is often inadequate, prompting recurrent land disputes.

The security of goodwill tenure remains fragile, as tenure differentiation between customary and statutory rights fosters inequality. Section 6 aims to blend traditional practices with statutory oversight, but weak enforcement and inadequate land administration systems have resulted in chronic tenure insecurity, hindering rural development, investment, and sustainability.¹⁰⁹

3.1.3 Certificates of Occupancy (C of O)

The Certificate of Occupancy (C of O) is the primary documentary proof of occupancy rights under the LUA. Issued by the Governor (for statutory rights) or Local Government (for customary rights), it formalizes the grantee's land interest. Though not full title, a C of O

¹⁰⁶ Note 103.

¹⁰⁷ LUA, s. 6(5).

¹⁰⁸ *Ibid*, s. 6(6).

¹⁰⁹ AT Abayomi, Note 105.

provides legal recognition, enabling mortgages, leases, and land transactions within the regulated tenure system.¹¹⁰

Nevertheless, the C of O is revocable through legally prescribed processes. Section 28 empowers the Governor to revoke rights for “overriding public interest” (e.g. infrastructure, health, defence), provided that fair compensation is given for unexhausted improvements. Judicial interpretations, such as in *CSS Bookshops Ltd v RTMCRS*,¹¹¹ have underlined the necessity of strict compliance with revocation procedures, including valid notice under Sections 28(6) – (7).

In *Dr Abdu-Ho v Mustapha Abubakar*,¹¹² the court held that revocation outside Section 28 procedures, such as via administrative correction under Section 5(2) is unlawful. Similarly, *Adole v Gwar*¹¹³ reinforced that statutory tenure continues until due revocation, and another grant over existing estates requires compliance with Section 28.

Despite these protections, the C of O is compromised by:

- Administrative delays, where issuance can take longer than a decade.
- Corruption, with officials setting unrealistic fees or soliciting bribes.
- Arbitrary revocations, as seen in recent political cases—e.g., Edo State’s revocation of Ize-Iyamu’s C of O in 2021, struck down in 2024 for violating procedural safeguards.¹¹⁴

While intended to reinforce tenure security and investment confidence, the C of O’s reality is mired by institutional inefficiencies and politicization. Its value depends on effective governance, transparency, and judicial enforcement, which remain inconsistent across Nigeria.

3.1.4 License and Permits: Legal and Administrative Constructs

¹¹⁰ A. Adeyinka and A. Adedolapo, ‘The Certificate of Occupancy as a Conclusive Proof of Title: Fact or Fiction’ (*SSRN*, January 17, 2019) <<https://ssrn.com/abstract=3324775>> accessed 25 June 2025.

¹¹¹ Note 104.

¹¹² *Dr Abdu-Ho v Mustapha Abubakar & Ors* (2016) JELR 33394 (CA).

¹¹³ Note 89.

¹¹⁴ *Pastor Ize-Iyamu and I. O. Farms Limited v. Edo State Government* (Unreported Suit No:B/637/2021 Judgment Delivered by Hon. Justice Peter Akhiehiero on 29 Stumper 2024).

Beyond occupancy rights, the LUA authorizes the issuance of licenses, permits, or concessionary grants for specific land uses—such as grazing, mining, forestry, or short-term commercial activities. These are governed by administrative regulations and do not confer proprietary rights; instead, they grant conditional, non-transferrable access under state control. Typically, short-term and purpose-bound, these licenses underscore the conditional nature of land access under the LUA. For instance, a grazing license issued under Section 6 allows pastoralists to occupy land for grazing but does not confer occupancy or alienable tenure. Similarly, mining permits or forestry concessions are regulated under separate statutes (e.g., Mineral and Mining Act),¹¹⁵ and their issuance is often contingent on environmental and development criteria.

The administrative nature of licenses means they can be withdrawn or suspended at will by issuing authorities. While revocation may require cause or notice, license holders cannot challenge deprivation of a renewable license as property loss, as it lacks guaranteed procedural protections afforded to occupancy rights. Economically, this limits long-term investment; license holders may hesitate to develop fixed infrastructure or invest greater capital given temporal uncertainty.¹¹⁶

Critically, the operation of licenses and permits within the LUA framework highlights the central role of administrative discretion in land governance. The LUA's licensing model reflects a balance between public interest (ensuring state control over resource exploitation) and individual access (allowing temporary land use). However, abuses can occur—such as selective issuance, favoritism, or coercive renewal—especially where licensing is linked with political patronage or corruption.¹¹⁷

¹¹⁵ Minerals and Mining Act 2007.

¹¹⁶ K. Balarabe, “Open Grazing Legislations and the Protection of Ethnic Minority Rights in Nigeria” (2021) 25(10) *The International Journal of Human Rights* 1835-1856.

¹¹⁷ *Ibid.*

In sum, while licenses and permits facilitate utilitarian use of land, their status falls short of proprietary guarantees, distinct from occupancy rights in both legal protection and investment support. Their widespread use further underscores the LUA's administrative nature, reinforcing that land under the Act is fundamentally a state-managed public resource, circumscribing the autonomy typically associated with property rights.

3.2 The Impact of the Act on the Doctrine of Estates in Land

3.2.1 Abolition of Freehold and Leasehold Estates

Before the LUA was enacted in 1978, property in Nigeria could be held as freehold—an absolute ownership interest derived from English common law—allowing an individual to hold land "in fee simple" in perpetuity, with broad discretion to sell, lease, or mortgage.¹¹⁸ Similarly, under the common law, leasehold estates of fixed terms (often 99 years) were recognized and freely alienable. Both interests underpinned a real estate market similar to that in England, facilitating investment and security of tenure.

The LUA radically transformed this landscape by abolishing freehold and reconfiguring all land interests as either statutory or customary rights of occupancy, held at the Governor's pleasure.¹¹⁹ Section 5 and 6 of the LUA mandate that grants of occupancy replace all previous tenures, effectively extinguishing pre-existing freehold and leasehold interests. The act required conversion of existing estates into 99-year leasehold-type C of O, eliminating indefinite ownership.

This shift redefined landholding as a statutory privilege rather than an inherent right. Holders are now tenants of the state, subject to administrative bureaucracy and revocation. This places occupants "deemed a tenant to the state," eliminating freehold at its root.¹²⁰

A significant case illustrating this principle is *Savannah Bank Ltd v Ajilo*,¹²¹ in which the Supreme Court held that even corporate freehold interests required the Governor's consent to mortgage, reinforcing that state control supersedes past freehold privileges. That case

¹¹⁸ Chaman Law Firm, 'Land Use Act and Land Tenure Systems; The Land Use Act Vs Traditional Land Tenure' (Chaman Law Firm, n.d) <<https://chamanlawfirm.com/land-use-act-and-land-tenure-systems/?>> accessed 25 June 2025.

¹¹⁹ *Ibid.*

¹²⁰ C. Uwaegbulam, 'Land Use Act: Between Powerful Governors and Oppressed Citizenry' (The Guardian, 29 June 2023) <<https://guardian.ng/news/land-use-act-between-powerful-governors-and-oppressed-citizenry/>> accessed 25 June 2025.

¹²¹ C. Uwaegbulam, Note 120.

highlighted the dramatic legal re-characterization: what was once privately owned property became state-regulated interest.

This redefinition had profound consequences. Investors found their real estate holdings now subject to centralized control and possible revocation. The requirement of governor's consent introduced administrative friction into property transfers, complicating transactions previously governed by market mechanisms.

Critics argue that abolishing freehold undermines tenure security and economic confidence. The 99-year tenure under C of O imposes renewal uncertainty, restricting long-term planning.¹²² Sociologically, this has created persistent tenure insecurity: once unfettered landowners became conditional occupants, holding land not by right, but by favour. Thus, the LUA's abolition of freehold and leasehold estates replaced private rights with statutory grants, shifting the foundation of landholding from autonomy to state control.

3.2.2 Centralization of Land Ownership in the Governor

Under Section 1 of the LUA, all land in a state—urban and rural—was vested in the state Governor, acting as trustee for the people. Urban land falls under the Governor; rural land under Local Government, but ultimate authority rests with the Governor. This was intended to standardize land administration across the country and curb speculation.

However, vesting absolute titling power in a single office became a recipe for centralization and bureaucratic domination. As described in Punch, the Governor, through the Land Use and Allocation Committee created by Section 2, holds almost unchecked discretion — appointing committees, granting occupancy, consenting to alienations, and revoking rights, with minimal

¹²² Chaman Law Firm, Note 118.

oversight.¹²³ In some states, these powers were personalized, creating what has been described as "totalitarian" land control.

This institutional structure lacks checks and balances, placing inefficient but powerful control in one office. This centralization undermines local autonomy: communities can no longer distribute land by custom; farmers and individuals must apply through state bureaucracies for access, regardless of historical claim. Traditional rights were effectively replaced by the Governor's fiat.

The system provides minimal recourse where governors abuse power in favour of political allies or deny access because of personal or partisan interests. Real estate developers like Babatunde Gbadamosi have described the LUA as "*unfair and retrogressive*", a barrier to investment because Governors can revoke occupancy at will.¹²⁴ These critiques highlight that centralization has led to politicization and sporadic abuse of land rights.

The centralized governance model has also been widely criticized academically. Scholars note it created a "monstrous fiefdom" under the Governor that conflated administrative, political, and judicial functions in one office.¹²⁵ Consequently, landholding in Nigeria has shifted from a legal-structural basis to an exercise of state discretion—rendering the Governor the de facto arbiter of all land rights, with communities reduced to rent-seeking applicants.

3.2.3 Effect on Land Transactions and Security of Tenure

The LUA requires the Governor's consent for all land alienations—including sales, leases, mortgages, and assignments—under Section 22. Without such consent, transactions are void

¹²³ A.S. Aina, 'Governor's Consent in Nigeria Land Law: Issues and Challenges' <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/386342446_GOVERNOR'S_CONSENT_IN_NIGERIA_LAND_LAW_ISSUES_AND_CHALLENGES> accessed 25 June 2025.

¹²⁴ The Guardian, 'Gbadamosi seeks repeal of Land Use Act' (9 December 2019) <<https://guardian.ng/news/gbadamosi-seeks-repeal-of-land-use-act/>> accessed 25 June 2025.

¹²⁵ O.E. Uzoamaka, N.C. Chisom and U.A. Nnamdi, "Critique of Nigerian Land Use Act of 1978" (2021) 11(6) *International Journal of Engineering Science* 28115-28120.

under Section 26. This centralization imposes significant barriers to otherwise legal real estate deals.

The consent requirement introduces administrative delays and cost escalation. As reported by The Punch, obtaining consent is bureaucratic, lengthy, and costly—an extortion opportunity within an inefficient public service. Research by Izinyon calls it a "nightmare" for certificate holders, full of "procedural wrangles, bottleneck, red-tapism".¹²⁶

Judicial responses have been mixed. In *Awojugbagbe Ltd v Chinukwe*,¹²⁷ the Supreme Court clarified that parties may negotiate and sign transfer deeds pending consent, and lack of consent does not necessarily void the contract – aiming to reduce commercial disruption. Meanwhile, *Ibrahim v Obaje*¹²⁸ further relaxed consequences, holding that where no public interest is involved and parties act in good faith, absence of consent does not invalidate the deal. These cases respond to the economic friction imposed by Section 22. Nonetheless, general tenure insecurity persists. Even with consent, the Governor retains power to revoke occupancy under Section 28 for “overriding public interest”, compensating only improvements not land market value. Ground rent remains the basis of compensation—a system criticized as oppressive and unfair.

Thus, while the LUA seeks to regulate land transactions, the centralized consent regime has made transactions cumbersome, expensive, and rife with abuse, undermining the security of tenure it was meant to protect.

3.2.4 Legal Critiques and Doctrinal Debates

¹²⁶ A.A. Izinyon, 'The Unending Battle on the Validity of Lack of Governor's Consent Under the Land Use Act: Has The Common Law Rule of Equity Resolved this?' (*Alexizinyon*, 28 June 2025) <alexizinyon.com/2020/10/09/the-unending-battle-on-the-validity-of-lack-of-governors-consent-under-the-land-use-act-has-the-common-law-rule-of-equity-resolved-this/> accessed 25 June 2025.

¹²⁷ *Awojugbagbe Light Ind Ltd v Chinukwe* [1995] 4 NWLR (Pt 390) 379.

¹²⁸ *Ibrahim v Obaje* [2019] 3 NWLR (Pt 1660) 389.

From its enactment, the LUA has faced substantial critique for reducing land to a state-conferred interest, conflicting with constitutional rights to property. Critics argue that the LUA substitutes inherent ownership for statutory privilege, rendering land tenure conditional upon bureaucratic favour.

Section 43 of the Constitution provides the right to acquire and own property, and Section 44 protects citizens from arbitrary deprivation. Legal scholars argue the LUA's expansive revocation powers and limited compensation framework contravene these guarantees. Particularly, compensation for unexhausted improvements—but not for land market value—is inconsistent with constitutional doctrines of just compensation.

Doctrinal debates have emerged over the nature of land interest under the LUA: are these true proprietary rights, or merely administrative privileges? Scholars describe a shift away from freehold toward state-granted tenure, incompatible with liberal property regimes.¹²⁹ Others argue that the LUA's rigid consent regime and narrow statutory construction necessarily erode private rights and should be reformed.¹³⁰

Judicial interpretations have moderated the LUA's harshest effects. In *Ibrahim v Obaje*,¹³¹ the Supreme Court rejected "mischievous" use of consent provisions to void transactions when no public interest was at issue, asserting the Act's Preamble protects citizens' land enjoyment. Nonetheless, core concerns remain unresolved—granting power without accountability.

Proposed reforms include amending Sections 22 to simplify consent regimes or automaticising them, aligning compensation standards with constitutional justice, and decentralizing authority to local governments in line with modern governance. Critics also demand greater constitutional scrutiny of the LUA's inherent conflicts with Section 43 and 44.

¹²⁹ O. E. Uzoamaka, N.C. Chisom and U.A. Nnamdi, Note 125.

¹³⁰ A. A. Izinyon, Note 126.

¹³¹ Note 128.

Thus, the LUA sits at a doctrinal crossroads: while rooted in public interest and egalitarian ideals, its real-world implementation has curtailed property autonomy, raised constitutional inconsistencies, and drawn calls for modern reform.

3.3 Acquisition of Land, Alienability, and Revocation of the Right of Occupancy Under the Act

3.3.1 Conditions for Valid Acquisition and Grants

Under the LUA, the process of land acquisition is primarily administrative. The LUA vests all land in each state of the federation in the Governor, who holds it in trust for the people and is responsible for allocation through the grant of statutory rights of occupancy.¹³² Local Governments are also empowered to grant customary rights of occupancy in rural areas under Section 6. However, these powers, although intended to ensure equitable access to land, are often exercised arbitrarily and in a manner that excludes marginalized communities.

A major concern is the absence of transparent mechanisms or enforceable criteria for land allocation. In practice, administrative discretion frequently overshadows merit, need, or customary entitlements. This system often leads to land grants being awarded to political elites, commercial developers, or foreign investors with strong political ties, sidelining poor communities and indigenous people with ancestral claims.¹³³ The situation is exacerbated by weak documentation, corruption, and lack of public oversight.

The discretion granted to Governors and Local Government chairpersons means that there are no uniform standards for determining eligibility or prioritizing applicants. Unlike market-driven systems where land is acquired through open bidding or by negotiation, land in Nigeria is often accessed through lobbying and patronage networks. This undermines the principles of

¹³² LUA, s. 5.

¹³³ I. Adewumi and F. Olokesusi, Note 91.

equality and justice, which are core to both Nigerian constitutional values and international human rights standards.¹³⁴

Moreover, indigenous groups have consistently complained that their ancestral lands are acquired or reallocated without consultation or regard for customary law. The LUA theoretically recognizes customary land rights through the grant of customary rights of occupancy; however, in practice, these are often treated as inferior and revocable at will. This was evident in *Adole v Gwar*,¹³⁵ where the Supreme Court affirmed that a customary right of occupancy, though recognized, is still subject to the Governor's overriding authority.

The result is a dual injustice: deprivation of land and denial of procedural fairness. Where large-scale land acquisition for development occurs without proper notice, participation, or compensation, the process violates not only the LUA's own procedural safeguards but also the constitutional right to property under Section 43 of the CFRN. Thus, while the LUA was designed to ensure fair land distribution and avoid land speculation, it has, in effect, entrenched a system where discretionary abuse thrives and legitimate communal claims are undermined.

3.3.2 Restrictions on Alienation and Consent of the Governor

The LUA imposes a statutory restriction on the transfer, mortgage, or alienation of land through Section 22, which mandates that the Governor's prior consent must be obtained before any holder of a statutory right of occupancy can validly alienate their interest. Similarly, under Section 21, the consent of the Local Government is required for the alienation of customary rights of occupancy. While the rationale behind this provision was to prevent indiscriminate fragmentation and preserve government oversight, in practice, it has become a tool of bureaucratic obstruction and control.

¹³⁴ B. Ibhawoh, Note 66.

¹³⁵ Note 89.

The requirement of consent effectively limits the proprietary autonomy of landholders. A person who has been granted a right of occupancy does not possess full legal ownership of the land; instead, they hold a derivative interest contingent upon continued compliance with state controls. Consequently, the LUA significantly restricts the alienability of land, thereby impeding its economic utility. Transactions such as sales, leases, or mortgages are often delayed or invalidated due to failure to obtain Governor's consent, creating uncertainties in land markets.¹³⁶

In the landmark case of *Savannah Bank v Ajilo*,¹³⁷ the Supreme Court held that failure to obtain Governor's consent rendered the transaction null and void. This decision, although doctrinally sound, has had significant implications for financial institutions and private investors, who often unknowingly engage in land transactions without the requisite consent. The requirement also introduces an avenue for corruption, as applicants often have to pay unofficial fees or face arbitrary delays to obtain consent.

Furthermore, the discretionary nature of the Governor's consent is problematic. There are no clear legal standards or timelines within which consent must be granted or refused. This allows public officials to manipulate the process for political or economic gain, frustrating legitimate transactions and undermining trust in land governance. The opacity surrounding the process contradicts the constitutional principles of fair administrative action and access to property rights under Sections 43 and 44 of the Constitution.

Critics argue that the requirement for consent should be retained only for first-time grants or large-scale transfers involving public land, and that private transactions between consenting adults should be free from government interference.¹³⁸ Some have also proposed that

¹³⁶ I. Adewumi and F. Olokesusi, Note 91.

¹³⁷ Note 53.

¹³⁸ R Ajayi, "Legal Constraints to Effective Land Use in Nigeria" (2021) 19 *African Research Review* 224.

administrative reforms such as digitization and fixed consent fees could reduce discretion and improve efficiency.

In essence, while Section 22 of the LUA may have been well-intentioned, its implementation has stifled the dynamism of the land economy, created barriers to housing finance, and allowed for discretionary abuse that undermines the rule of law and proprietary freedom.

3.3.3 Procedure for Revocation and Compensation Mechanisms

The LUA grants the Governor extensive powers to revoke rights of occupancy under Section 28, particularly for reasons of “overriding public interest.” However, the term “overriding public interest” is broadly defined and vulnerable to abuse. Revocation is often carried out without genuine public need or adequate consultation with affected landholders. While the intention of the law was to enable the state to acquire land for developmental purposes such as infrastructure, education, or health, practice has shown a tendency for revocations to favour private development projects disguised as public interest.

Section 28(2) defines overriding public interest to include urban planning, mining, oil operations, and economic development. Yet, in many instances, land has been revoked and reallocated to private investors, contrary to the spirit of the Act. This was highlighted in *Osho v Foreign Finance Corporation*,¹³⁹ where the Court held that revocation must be for a genuine public purpose and that the Governor must act in good faith. However, judicial enforcement has been inconsistent, and many revocations go unchallenged due to legal illiteracy or lack of access to justice.

Compensation mechanisms under Section 29 of the LUA provide only for unexhausted improvements on the land—not the land itself. This means that where land is bare or

¹³⁹ Note 68.

undeveloped, no compensation is payable, regardless of its sentimental, ancestral, or potential market value. This approach significantly devalues the essence of landholding, especially for customary users and smallholders who may not have formalized or improved their holdings but rely on the land for livelihood and identity.

This narrow scope of compensation has been a major source of grievance, especially in rural and peri-urban communities. Critics argue that it violates the constitutional guarantee under *Section 44* of the 1999 Constitution, which provides for prompt and adequate compensation when property is compulsorily acquired. Furthermore, international best practices under instruments like the *African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (ACHPR)*,¹⁴⁰ to which Nigeria is a party, advocate full compensation for both land and improvements, regardless of title status.

Administrative procedures for revocation are often flawed. Notifications/Notices are either not served properly or not served at all. In some cases, affected parties become aware only after bulldozers arrive on site. Moreover, there is no statutory requirement for participatory processes or public hearings before revocation is carried out. These gaps violate due process and have led to numerous social conflicts, evictions, and litigations.

The revocation and compensation regime under the LUA thus reflect a deeply utilitarian view of land, reducing it to an object of state control rather than a source of livelihood, culture, and dignity for its holders.

3.3.4 Judicial Decisions on Acquisition and Revocation Disputes

Over the years, Nigerian courts have been called upon to interpret and enforce the provisions of the LUA in the context of land acquisition and revocation. These judicial decisions reflect a

¹⁴⁰ African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (adopted 27 June 1981, entered into force 21 October 1986) 1520 UNTS 217.

tension between upholding the authority of the Governor and protecting the constitutional rights of individuals. In *Nkwocha v Governor of Anambra State*,¹⁴¹ the Supreme Court held that the LUA had effectively extinguished all previous landholding systems, vesting control in the Governor. This case confirmed the centralizing intent of the LUA but also raised concerns about the erosion of customary land rights.

Similarly, in *Osho v Foreign Finance Corporation*,¹⁴² the Supreme Court emphasized that while the Governor has power to revoke land, such revocation must be based on genuine public interest. The court's decision highlighted the need for procedural fairness and transparency, warning against arbitrary use of revocation powers. However, despite these pronouncements, courts have often deferred to the Governor's discretion, especially where revocation is formally stated to be for public interest.

A notable case that tested the boundaries of this discretion is *Shell Petroleum Development Co. Ltd v Isaiah*,¹⁴³ where the court held that the Governor's power to revoke rights of occupancy must not violate the right to fair hearing. The case reinforced the idea that even administrative acts must adhere to principles of natural justice. However, enforcement of such judicial dicta has remained weak.

The courts have also grappled with issues surrounding compensation. In *Goldmark Nigeria Ltd v Ibafor Co. Ltd*,¹⁴⁴ the Supreme Court reaffirmed that compensation must be adequate and prompt in accordance with constitutional requirements. However, in practice, what constitutes "adequate" remains contentious, especially when compensation is limited only to unexhausted improvements and excludes the land's market value.

¹⁴¹ Note 58.

¹⁴² Note 68.

¹⁴³ Note 97.

¹⁴⁴ Note 82.

There is a growing call for the judiciary to adopt a more rights-based approach when interpreting the LUA. This includes stricter scrutiny of executive actions, mandatory public interest verification, and broader interpretation of compensation entitlements. Judicial activism in this area is critical to counterbalance the discretionary powers conferred on Governors by the Act and to safeguard the constitutional right to property.

3.4 Legal Frameworks for Ownership and Protection of Land in Nigeria

3.4.1 Constitutional Provisions (Section 43 & 44 CFRN 1999)

Sections 43 and 44 of the CFRN 1999 (as amended 2011) provide the foundation for property rights in Nigeria. Section 43 grants every Nigerian the right to acquire and own immovable property anywhere in the country, subject only to the law. Section 44 further strengthens this right by protecting individuals from compulsory acquisition of their property except in the manner and for the purposes prescribed by law, and upon the prompt payment of adequate compensation.

These constitutional protections signify that the right to property is both recognized and protected under Nigerian law. However, when juxtaposed with the provisions of the LUA 1978, a tension becomes apparent. The LUA, particularly Sections 1 and 28, vests all land in a state in the Governor and grants the Governor sweeping powers to revoke rights of occupancy for reasons deemed to be in the “public interest.” While this may appear to align with Section 44(1)(a) of the Constitution, which allows for compulsory acquisition for public purposes, the interpretation and application of what constitutes “public purpose” have often been fraught with abuse, ambiguity, and lack of transparency.

This contradiction has been the subject of judicial consideration. In *Nkwocha v. Governor of*

Anambra State,¹⁴⁵ the Supreme Court held that while the LUA is valid and constitutional, it must be applied in accordance with the provisions of the Constitution. The courts have reiterated that failure to follow due process or to pay adequate compensation renders a revocation unlawful. In *Osho v. Foreign Finance Corporation*,¹⁴⁶ it was held that revocation of land without adequate compensation violates the Constitution and is subject to judicial review.

Nevertheless, despite these judicial pronouncements, in practice, landowners frequently face challenges such as delay or outright denial of compensation, and the lack of clear procedures for contesting revocation. The discretion conferred on the Governor has often been exercised arbitrarily, undermining the protective intent of the Constitution. Hence, although the Constitution enshrines the right to property, the LUA appears to dilute that right through its broad delegation of land administration powers to state authorities, thereby creating a gap between constitutional ideals and administrative realities.

3.4.2 The Land Use Act 1978

The LUA was enacted to reform land tenure, reduce inequality in land ownership, and facilitate land access for development purposes. Its central innovation was the nationalization of land by vesting all land in each state in the Governor to hold in trust for the people, as provided under Section 1. This shift from private ownership to state-controlled occupancy was intended to end the chaos and inequality resulting from the pre-1978 dual systems of customary and statutory landholding.

However, over four decades after its enactment, the LUA has become a source of considerable legal and socio-economic concern. One of the primary criticisms is that the Act undermines

¹⁴⁵ Note 58.

¹⁴⁶ Note 68.

liberal conceptions of property rights by eliminating fee simple ownership and converting all landholdings into rights of occupancy, either statutory or customary. These rights are not absolute and are subject to revocation and the discretionary control of the Governor, as seen in Section 28.

A significant challenge to the reform or repeal of the LUA lies in its constitutional entrenchment under *Section 315(5)(d) of the 1999 Constitution*¹⁴⁷, which provides:

*‘Nothing in this Constitution shall invalidate the following enactments, that is—
(d) the Land Use Act, and each of the other Acts mentioned in this section; and
the provisions of those Acts shall continue to have effect as Federal enactments
and shall be deemed to be an integral part of this Constitution.’*

This provision elevates the LUA to a special status, making its amendment a constitutional matter requiring a two-thirds majority of both the National Assembly and state Houses of Assembly. This has made legislative reform extremely difficult, despite widespread calls for amendment. *The Presidential Technical Committee on Land Reform (PTCLR)*, for instance, has repeatedly recommended a review of the LUA to address issues of tenure insecurity, access to land, and bureaucratic bottlenecks.

Furthermore, judicial interpretation of the LUA has not always clarified its ambiguities. In *Adole v. Gwar*,¹⁴⁸ the Supreme Court reaffirmed that a Certificate of Occupancy does not confer title to land, but only evidences a right of occupancy. This uncertainty often undermines land security and hinders investment.

The rigidity and opacity of the LUA’s provisions especially those concerning Governor’s consent, revocation, and compensation have bred corruption and inefficiency in land administration. The Act’s inflexibility in responding to contemporary realities such as

¹⁴⁷ as amended 2011

¹⁴⁸ Note 89.

urbanization, population growth, and land speculation further exposes its outdated nature. Hence, while the LUA sought to establish a uniform and equitable land tenure system, its continued application has constrained property rights and hampered land reform.

3.4.3 State Land Laws and Planning Regulations

Though the LUA vests land ownership in the Governor of each state, it coexists with a range of other state laws and urban planning regulations that impact land administration. States enact laws regulating physical planning, development control, building permits, and environmental management, among others. These state-level legal instruments such as the 2015 Land Registration Law of Lagos State,¹⁴⁹ while essential for sustainable land use, often operate in tension with the LUA, leading to jurisdictional conflicts and administrative overlaps.

One notable issue arises when a holder of a C of O issued under the LUA seeks to develop land without fulfilling state physical planning requirements. In such situations, state agencies have been known to demolish buildings or revoke planning permits, even where the landholder possesses a valid statutory right of occupancy. In *Lagos State Development and Property Corporation v. Foreign Finance Corporation*,¹⁵⁰ the court recognized that even with a C of O, compliance with other state laws, including planning regulations, remains mandatory.

Additionally, the existence of multiple agencies with overlapping mandates—such as the Ministry of Lands, Physical Planning Departments, and Urban Development Authorities—often creates confusion and opportunities for rent-seeking. In some instances, applicants are required to obtain multiple approvals, adding to the cost and time of land development, thus stifling investment and access to affordable housing.¹⁵¹

¹⁴⁹ Lagos State Land Registration Law 2015.

¹⁵⁰ *Lagos State Development and Property Corporation v. Foreign Finance Corporation* (1987) 1 NWLR (Pt. 50) 413.

¹⁵¹ I.O. Odionu and I.K. Oraegbunam, “The Status of Certificate of Occupancy under the Land Registration Law 2015 of Lagos State: A Wake-up Call on Other States in Nigeria” (2021) 3 *International Journal of Comparative Law and Legal Philosophy* 50.

Moreover, the enforcement of these state laws is frequently inconsistent or arbitrary. For example, while planning laws require that land be developed within a specific period, revocation for “non-use” is often applied selectively, especially against politically vulnerable or economically disadvantaged individuals.¹⁵²

Another area of conflict is in compensation and resettlement. State laws may prescribe different thresholds or procedures for compensation in cases of compulsory acquisition than those found in the LUA. This often results in legal disputes over which law prevails, particularly where claimants allege violations of their rights to fair treatment and due process.

Thus, while state land and planning laws are essential for regulating urban growth and environmental sustainability, the absence of harmonization with the LUA leads to inconsistencies in implementation. This legal fragmentation contributes to tenure insecurity and undermines the efficiency of Nigeria’s land governance framework.

3.4.4 Human Rights Frameworks: Right to Property and Access to Justice

Nigeria’s obligations under International Human Rights Law further reinforce the right to property and access to justice. The *ACHPR*, ratified and domesticated into Nigerian law via the *African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act*,¹⁵³ affirms in Article 14 that the right to property shall be guaranteed and may only be encroached upon in the public interest and in accordance with appropriate laws.

However, the LUA’s framework and its implementation often fall short of these human rights standards. Revocation of rights of occupancy without genuine public purpose, lack of adequate compensation, and failure to provide affected persons with access to timely legal redress are persistent concerns. In *Archbishop Anthony Olubunmi Okogie v. Attorney-General of Lagos State*,¹⁵⁴ the Supreme Court held that while rights may be regulated, they cannot be

¹⁵² *Ibid.*

¹⁵³ African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act Cap A9 LFN 2004.

¹⁵⁴ *Archbishop Anthony Olubunmi Okogie v. Attorney-General of Lagos State* (1981) 2 NCLR 337.

extinguished arbitrarily without due process. Yet in practice, abuses of discretionary power under the LUA continue.

Access to justice is also hindered by systemic barriers such as legal illiteracy, poverty, high litigation costs, and prolonged delays in court processes. Many victims of unlawful revocation or denial of compensation are unable to pursue legal redress due to these obstacles. Furthermore, there is a dearth of public legal aid mechanisms to support land-related claims, especially for vulnerable populations.

Another critical concern is the inadequacy of institutional oversight. The LUA provides minimal avenues for independent review or appeal of the Governor's actions. This violates the human rights principle of accountability and the right to an effective remedy, as articulated in *Article 7 of the ACHPR*.

Although courts have in some instances asserted property rights against state encroachment, enforcement remains inconsistent.¹⁵⁵ Moreover, where judicial declarations are made in favour of landowners, compliance by government agencies is often delayed or ignored, further eroding trust in the justice system.

Consequently, despite Nigeria's human rights commitments, the LUA's operational realities often compromise the enjoyment of the right to property and meaningful access to justice. Legal reform is essential to harmonize domestic land laws with international standards and ensure that property rights are not only recognized in theory but also upheld in practice.

3.5 Conclusion

In conclusion, the LUA has profoundly redefined the legal landscape of land rights in Nigeria, shifting the paradigm from private ownership to a regime of state-controlled occupancy. While the Act sought to unify land administration, reduce inequality, and promote orderly

¹⁵⁵ See *Bello v Diocesan Synod of Lagos* (1973) 1 All NLR (Pt. I) 247, *Governor of Lagos State v Ojukwu* (1986) 1 NWLR (Pt. 18) 621.

development, it has had far-reaching implications for private proprietary rights. The introduction of statutory and customary rights of occupancy has replaced fee simple ownership, thereby subjecting all land interests to the discretion of state authorities. Although certificates of occupancy offer some level of formalization, they remain vulnerable to revocation and fail to convey absolute ownership, which limits their utility as instruments of economic empowerment and investment security.

The centralization of land ownership in the Governor has created a bureaucratic and often opaque system that hinders land transactions, limits tenure security, and gives rise to abuse of power in the name of public interest. Judicial decisions have occasionally offered some redress, but inconsistencies and weak enforcement continue to frustrate meaningful reform. The Act also presents unresolved tensions with constitutional property rights, revealing the need for a more balanced and rights-oriented land governance framework. A comprehensive review of the Act is therefore imperative to reconcile its provisions with Nigeria's constitutional and developmental aspirations.

CHAPTER FOUR

THE LAND USE ACT: PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS

4.0 Introduction

The LUA was a transformative legislative intervention aimed at addressing Nigeria's fragmented and often inequitable land tenure systems. Prior to its enactment, landholding in Nigeria was governed by a complex mosaic of customary, statutory, and received English laws, leading to legal uncertainties, uneven access, and widespread land disputes. The Act sought to harmonize these divergent regimes by vesting all land in each state (except those belonging to the Federal Government or its agencies) in the state governor, who holds it in trust for the people. It introduced statutory and customary rights of occupancy, ostensibly to promote uniformity, access, and fairness in land administration.

In the United Kingdom, Land law is a complex and dynamic area of law; understanding the key principles, legislation, and registration requirements is crucial for anyone involved in property transactions or ownership. The concept of land ownership in the UK is rooted in the Crown and interest are formed via the principle of freehold, leasehold, easements, covenants, mortgages etc. Freehold ownership gives the owner absolute rights over the land, subject to any legal restrictions or obligations whilst leasehold is limited to a number of specific years to the lessee. In here, several legislations are made which regulates the administration of lands.¹⁵⁶ For. e.g. The planning and compulsory purchase act 2004, Land registration act 2002 as well as other enacted contemporary laws. Additionally, in the western Australia region, lands are reserved and held by the Aboriginal Land Trust, whom hold lands for many western Australian aboriginal communities. *The Aboriginal Land Trust ALT and Aboriginal Affairs Planning*

¹⁵⁶ UK Property Law Expertise <<https://property-practice-law-sqe.co.uk/land-law-in-the-uk-a-comprehensive-guide-to-key-principles-and-legislation/>> accessed 14 July, 2025.

Authority Act – AAPA are landholders issuing leases to people or organizations in accordance with Section 41 of the Aboriginal Affairs Planning Authority Act 1972. In the above circumstances any Aboriginal person or people can apply for a lease on the Aboriginal Land Trust reserve, likewise Government agencies are offered Crown lands, reserved for purposes of public interest; when demonstrated to be for the use and benefit of the Aboriginal people. In Tasmania, there is no Aboriginal Land Rights Legislative regime but the Aboriginal Land Act, Tasmania acknowledges the indigenous people of Tasmania and provides for an establishment of an elected Aboriginal Land Council to hold and manage land of historical significance. The Act provides for 12 parcels of culturally significant lands. Other regions e.g. Queens, South Australia, the capital territory have unique and significant laws peculiar to each of the regions in relation to land use. As Australia have no national legislation on land administration.¹⁵⁷

Despite its good intentions, the Act has generated substantial legal and socio-economic challenges. It has redefined ownership in a manner that diminishes proprietary interests and subjects land rights to the discretionary powers of the state. The requirement of governor's consent for most land transactions, broad revocation powers under the guise of public purpose, and the centralization of land authority have all weakened individual security of tenure. This chapter critically examines these challenge of tenure system, housing, obtaining governor's consent, compulsory acquisition, inadequate payment as compensation and other prevalent factors in present times which has shaped the quest for modern reform, thereby bridging the gap in present times; the conflict between federal and state powers under the Act, and evaluates the prospects for reform, reinterpretation, and alignment with constitutional and democratic values. These key factors are of pertinent for purposes.

¹⁵⁷ Land Rights Legislation - Agreements, Treaties and Negotiated Settlements <<https://www.atns.net.au/land-rights-legislation-1#>> accessed 16th July, 2025.

4.1 The Challenges Posed by the Act vis-à-vis the Exercise of Proprietary Rights

A primary criticism of the LUA is the radical but contentious centralization of land title. *Section 1* vests all land within a Nigerian state in its Governor, who holds it “in trust” for the people. Rather than absolute property, individuals now merely possess a “right of occupancy” – statutory or customary – which is strictly subordinate to state authority. It can be revoked by the Governor under Section 28 for matters of “overriding public interest,” a term criticized as nebulous and subjectively applied.¹⁵⁸ This systemic arrangement has undermined tenure security, especially in rural zones where land is a cornerstone of cultural identity and social cohesion. In practice, revocation under Section 28 often occurs arbitrarily, with insufficient or untimely compensation, leaving occupiers disenfranchised. The courts have insisted on strict compliance with notice and purpose requirements—illustrated in *Obikoya & Sons Ltd v Governor of Lagos State*,¹⁵⁹ where revocation was invalidated due to failure to specify reasons in the notice, as is unauthorized under Section 28(6) & (7). Further compounding land insecurity is the consent requirement in Section 22 of the Act. Any transfer, assignment, mortgage, or lease necessitates gubernatorial approval. In reality, these slow adjudications breed corruption, extortion and unpredictability – significantly impeding land transactions and constraining the ability to use land as collateral. Beyond discrimination at the individual level, the LUA’s imposition of a uniform, state-centric land tenure system frictionally collides with Nigeria’s plural legal heritage, which includes customary and religious land rights. This legal hybridity animates conflict, with urban and rural dynamics exacerbating ambiguity over which system holds precedence. Desperate land rights frameworks undermine investor confidence, obstruct land reform, and stall expansion in agriculture and housing sectors.¹⁶⁰

¹⁵⁸ O.E. Uzoamaka, N.C. Chisom and U.A. Nnamdi, Note 125.

¹⁵⁹ *Obikoya & Sons Ltd v Governor of Lagos State* (1987) 1 NWLR (Pt 50) 385 C.A.

¹⁶⁰ O.E. Uzoamaka, N.C. Chisom and U.A. Nnamdi, *Ibid.*

In summary, although the LUA envisioned equitable land distribution, its vesting of power in the Governor, the discretionary revocation of occupancy rights, and convoluted administrative requirements undermine absolute proprietary ownership. This leaves landholders vulnerable to arbitrary governance/ whims and caprices, threatening economic development and socio-cultural stability.

4.2 Discrepancy Between the Powers of the Federal Government and the Governor of a State Under the Act: Position of the Law

A critical legal tension under the LUA is the parallel jurisdiction exercised by the Federation over certain lands and resources. While Section 1 of the LUA empowers Governors to administer all land within their states, the Constitution reserves special land categories such as federal territories, mineral resources, and federal infrastructure for federal oversight under Section 44(3) CFRN 1999.

One notable legal dispute occurred in *Governor of Lagos State v Ojukwu*,¹⁶¹ centered on contested land usage. The case underscored the consequences of overlapping regulatory regimes, where a Federal agency purportedly exercised authority over state land. Similar friction has been reported between Governors and national bodies like Nigerian National Petroleum Company over land access for extractive operations.

The Supreme Court attempted clarity in *Attorney-General of Lagos State v Attorney-General of the Federation*,¹⁶² affirming that lands not explicitly designated federal belong to state governors. Yet, ambiguity remains whenever “public purpose” is invoked, especially regarding dual jurisdiction and where concurrent powers overlap.

These tensions produce uncertainty for landholders and investors. Developers unsure whether state or federal permission is required may face project delays. Moreover, competing claims

¹⁶¹ Note 154.

¹⁶² *Attorney-General of Lagos State v Attorney-General of the Federation* (2003) 12 NWLR (Pt 833) 1.

often lead to litigation, increasing risk and diminishing enforceability of tenure. This uncertainty works against efforts at economic development, reinforcing a trust deficit in Institutional land governance across jurisdictions.

4.3 The Land Tenure System and Proprietary Rights

The land tenure system in Nigeria prior to the promulgation of the Land Use Act 1978, encouraged freehold title of estates and absolute fee simple interest in land. Lands were communally owned and utilized as a major source of survival, usually headed by the communal chief or village head. Lands are subject matter of compulsory acquisition, planning and acquisition by virtue of compulsory acquisition or overriding public interest, including compensation. A renowned author Harold Laski once mentioned that:

*“the man of property has a stake in the country. He is protected from the fear of starvation He can protect his children against the dread of want. He can develop in them the tastes which gives them also joy in the life creative.....”*¹⁶³

Same private land in this context is traditionally recognized and protected by the constitution and common law of pre-colonial times, same as common law is in reflection of cases, e.g. the case of *Rylands v. Fletcher*.¹⁶⁴

On inception of the act, it become inevitable that the letters of the act remain docile or inapplicable to the system of landholding. The implication is that, there emerged an invasive shift in land dynamics distinct from its known peculiarities to an unknown and bizarre norm. The distinct peculiarities of communal land, family land, the kola tenancy in force in medieval times, were completely eroded due to the emergence of the Act, which preferred a lesser interest.

¹⁶³ Harold J. Laski, *A Grammar of Politics* (George Allen and Unwin Publishers Ltd. Boston and Sydney, 1967) Chapter 5 at P. 173

¹⁶⁴ *Rylands v. Fletcher* 1868 UKHL LR 3 HL 3

4.4 Urban Development, Infrastructures Building, Low-cost Housing Schemes and Joint Development Agreements in modern times

The need for optimum utilization of land in this current dispensation have become an objective for individual with interest in Land as well as the state, as same is of inestimable value. In recent times, the government acquires lands, for projects on availability of low-cost housing, affordable shelters for low-income earners and the average citizen in the state.

In the light of modern trends, eccentric developments in relation to land have now emerged; multiple interest on land with distinct and well-structured basis, without interference on the rights of other mutual interest holders. In addition, the quest for suitable accommodation, with shortage of funds and land, resulted in a unique arrangement in development agreements. In Nigeria, most State Governments have embarked on joint development agreements with private companies so as to alleviate housing problems in the states¹⁶⁵ as well as curbing the exorbitant rent charged by landlords on ridiculous term of year(s) of occupation. A joint development agreement comprises of an arrangement between a land owner and a developer, to develop parcel of land for mutual benefits via the applicable models; -

- A Land owner on agreement with a Developer to develop land on fixed consideration agreement with a Developer, which may be in cash or kind.
- On agreement with a Developer to construct buildings and to share the built-up area in a definite arrangement.
- A land owner may contribute his land to a partnership firm, whom then acts as a Developer and on completion of the project, profits are shared.¹⁶⁶

Common terms likely associated with *Joint Development Agreement (JDA)* are: price sharing and profit sharing, property ownership and license to construct or lease to construct, continuous

¹⁶⁵ Oyo state Government has concluded arrangement with UACN property to build houses for the low- and middle-class income earners, see Oyo State bulletin No. 18 (2014).

¹⁶⁶ Income Tax Department (Government of India), 'Joint Development Agreements (JDA) *Tutorials*, 2025) <<https://incometaxindia.gov.in/tutorials/66.joint-development-agreements.pdf>> accessed 20 October 2025.

co-operation between owner and the builder/developer.¹⁶⁷ The sole aim for government on embarking on development agreements is solely “in the best interest of the public” unlike the profit motivated rationale for private developers and private land owners in this context; source of funding for the projects do differ as the government grant tax concessions or incentives as part of its funds contribution whilst private land owners/developers resort to aid from financial institutions etc.

It’s important to state that development agreement is not outrightly a lease but possesses the characteristics of a lease with its own distinct features. Common feature is the certainty of parties, property and term, exclusive possession, right of reversion upon expiration of the development agreement and consent which become inevitable at peculiar stages of the contract, upon completion. In here the land owner and developer agrees that the developer makes improvements on the land or build at its own cost, within a specified time and after which the landowner sub-leases the property to the developer, for a term of years, so as to enable him recoup his investments with profits via subletting same to third party. Whilst on other circumstances, there may be a joint agreement to build and the units apportioned in a certain percentage of investments or same be sold and profits shared on basis of investment input.

Nonetheless, there is need for such development to be backed with requisite laws, making its operation more solidified and subject to legal scrutiny whatsoever. Although no direct legislation exists with respect to development agreements in Nigeria, but same is a subject of multiple legislations which often amount to overlapping of the laws. The legislations provided:

1. **Constitution:** Sections 43 and 44 of the constitution¹⁶⁸ opines that every citizen shall have the right to acquire any immovable property in Nigeria; on the other hand, section

¹⁶⁷ *Ibid.*

¹⁶⁸ 2011

44 dwells on compensation thereof for any immovable property obtained compulsorily from its owner.

2. **The Land Use Act:** relevant statute to development agreement, although the land use act made no express provision for of development agreement as a interest in land. But it's presumed to be an arrangement between a land owner and developers and on consideration of recoup of investment or money expended. On issue of obtaining Governor's Consent, same is irrelevant at the construction stage, but upon completion and sublease of the investment to the developer for recoup of his investments, it becomes pertinent for consent of the governor to be first had and obtained.

S. 22 of the Land Use Act¹⁶⁹:

“is shall be unlawful for the holder of a statutory right of occupancy granted by the governor to alienate his right of occupancy or any part thereof by assignment, mortgage, transfer of possession, sub-lease or otherwise howsoever without the consent of the Governor first had and obtained”

On further interpretation, it can be said that development agreement is a conveyance in itself.

S.2 (1) of the Property and Conveyancing Law¹⁷⁰ provides that;

‘A conveyance is a mortgage, charge, lease, assent, vesting declaration and every other instrument except a will’

On reliance on the PCL¹⁷¹, conveyance denotes a document which includes the act of performing various transactions or functions related to creation, transfer of, variation etc... including the conduct of search and perfection of instrument. The lacunas in non-inclusion of

¹⁶⁹ 1978

¹⁷⁰ Property and Conveyancing Law 1959.

¹⁷¹ *Ibid.*

development agreement in the legislations, permits the act of intrusion of compound applicable laws in the circumstance.

On application of development agreement in Nigeria, the Urban and Regional Planning Laws¹⁷² contributes to a large extent on the procedural stance, ensuring that the applications and all attached documents meets the standard requirement. It outlines the requisite documents and payments for development permits and subject to approval. On other areas of complexities e.g. mortgage transaction, there are no prescribed provisions on mortgage transaction in relation to development agreements. The lacuna or question in issue, being the legal stance where the terms of the agreement, permits a developer to mortgage his interest and use of the developed property for a specified time as a collateral, on default, can the mortgagee exercise its right of sale? A legal mortgage is executed by granting demise of a term of years absolute subject to cessation on redemption¹⁷³, as assignment of the totality of the mortgagor's interest is not possible.¹⁷⁴

Where a default emerges, the bank is authorized by law to enforce its right of sale but in the circumstance and due to the peculiarities of the leasehold interest of the developer, the mortgagor can enter into possession, invoke the covenant to repay within the term of years so granted to the mortgagor (developer) utilizing its viable mechanisms to recover all sum due without more.

Without further ado, development agreement is a viable plan with usefulness in providing low cost shelter/housing mainly utilized by the government and private developers. However, the rationale for involvement by the Government is predicated on the sole benefit of the people, but the need of subsidized rent for its citizens has been watered down, as inflation, high cost of living and other inflationary trends has adversely robbed off the advantage. Notwithstanding,

¹⁷² The Lagos State Urban and Regional Planning Board Law, Cap L52, Laws of Lagos State 2003, 2010

¹⁷³ S. 108(1) (a) Cap. 100 Laws of Western Nigeria 1959

¹⁷⁴ I.O. Smith Note 24.

with necessary checks and policy implementation by the government, curated to cure these defects, the objectives becomes feasible.

4.5 Obtaining of Governor's Consent

Under the LUA, any person who holds a right of occupancy, whether granted directly by the governor or deemed to exist under customary law, cannot transfer, mortgage, or otherwise alienate that land without first obtaining the governor's consent. This requirement is clearly stated in Section 22 of the LUA. The main idea behind this rule is to ensure that the government maintains control and oversight over all land transactions in the state. However, in practice, this provision has created serious difficulties for landowners, investors, and financial institutions.

The importance of this consent requirement was confirmed in the famous case of *Savannah Bank of Nigeria Ltd v. Ajilo*.¹⁷⁵ In that case, the plaintiff had executed a deed of mortgage in favour of the defendant without obtaining the governor's consent. When the plaintiff defaulted, the bank attempted to sell the mortgaged property, but the court ruled that the transaction was invalid because the required consent had not been obtained. The court emphasized that it is unlawful for any holder of a statutory right of occupancy to alienate his interest without prior consent of the governor. Interestingly, the court also held that the plaintiff, who failed to obtain consent, could not take advantage of his own wrongdoing to invalidate the mortgage and escape his debt obligation.

This decision has made the governor's consent a critical step in all land transactions. Yet, the process of obtaining this consent is often slow, bureaucratic, and prone to corruption. Many people either avoid formal registration or resort to unofficial channels, which weakens the system and reduces government revenue. The consent requirement, while meant to protect

¹⁷⁵ *Savannah Bank of Nigeria Ltd v. Ajilo* (1989) 1 NWLR (Pt. 97) 305.

public interest, has therefore become a major obstacle to land development and credit access in Nigeria. Scholars and practitioners have repeatedly called for reforms to simplify the process or to delegate consent powers to local authorities for minor transactions. The current system, if not reviewed, continues to frustrate private investment and weaken land security in the country.¹⁷⁶

4.6 Acquisition of Land

The LUA gives the government the power to take over land for public purposes, but this power must be exercised fairly and within the limits of the law. This process is known as **revocation** of rights of occupancy, and it is governed by Section 28 of the Act. A governor can revoke a right of occupancy for two main reasons: first, when the land is required for overriding public interest, and second, when it is needed for public projects such as roads, schools, hospitals, or mining and oil pipeline purposes.

*Section 3 of the Public Acquisition Act*¹⁷⁷ provides thus:

“where any land is required for a public purpose of the federation or for a public purpose of a state, the President in the former case and the Governor of the State concerned in respect of any land within the state in the latter case may acquire such lands for an estateunder the provisions of the act”

Howbeit, its lawful where lands so acquired are on such justifiable grounds, so outlined and the basis of acquisition by the Government. The terms “revocation of right of occupancy for public purpose” and “compulsory land acquisition for public purpose” appear to be synonymous, because if either of them (is carried out by the government), it has the effect of expropriating land or extinguishing all existing rights in the land. It is in this light that the

¹⁷⁶ J.A. Yakubu, *Land Law in Nigeria* (Macmillan Publishers, 2019) p. 142.

¹⁷⁷ Ibid

theoretical basis of compulsory acquisition will be used to explain the term “revocation of right of occupancy” being the term used by the LUA; an inexorable and inherent component of right of occupancy¹⁷⁸. According to a renowned author, Compulsory Land Acquisition is the forcible taking or acquisition of private lands (communal or individual) for public benefits or purposes. The revocation theory in this instance is covered by provisions of *Section 28 – 33 of the Land Use Act* and the word “revocation” was not defined by the *Land Use Act*, otherwise referred to as LUA, but it has the effect of extinguishing all rights of a possessor of right of occupancy.

Under the provisions of the afore-mentioned section, precisely S. 28(1)(2) ground for overriding public purposes were disclosed to be;

- Alienation by way of assignment, mortgage, sub-lease etc...contrary to the provisions of the Act.
- For public purposes within the state or purpose of the Federation
- The requirement of land for mining purposes or oil purposes or any other purpose connected therewith.
- The requirement of the land for extraction of building materials.

In the case of *Obikoya & Sons Ltd v. The Governor of Lagos State and Another*,¹⁷⁹ the court gave important guidance on how this power should be used. The court held that although the Act allows the governor to revoke a certificate of occupancy for public purposes, such revocation must comply with due process. The person whose land is being taken must be properly notified, and the reason for revocation must be clearly stated, even though the Act

¹⁷⁸ Hon. Justice I. A. Umezulike, OFR.FCIARB on A B C of Contemporary Land Law in Nigeria (Revised and Enlarged Edition) 2013.

¹⁷⁹ *Obikoya & Sons Ltd v. The Governor of Lagos State* (1987) 1 NWLR (Pt. 50) 385.

does not expressly require it. This ensures transparency and protects the affected person's rights.

Unfortunately, in many cases, revocation is carried out without proper notice or without clear justification of public purpose. Some revocations are politically motivated or influenced by private interests, contrary to the intention of the law. When such abuses occur, the courts often face the difficult task of balancing state powers with individual rights. The principle emerging from case law is that while the state has legitimate power to acquire land for the greater good, it must not do so arbitrarily or in bad faith.¹⁸⁰ It is worthy to note that the revocation is usually initiated by a notice by or on behalf of the Head of the Federal Military Government and duly signed by an authorized public officer by the Governor. Same position having been reiterated by the courts in *Osho V. Foreign Finance Corporation*¹⁸¹ on need of valid notice issued upon revocation of a right of occupancy. The supreme court opined that:

“where a right of occupancy is stated to be revoked for public purpose, there is the need to spell out the public purpose in the notice of revocation.”

The requirement of notice and clear justification is therefore vital. It prevents secret or unjust expropriation and gives the affected party a chance to challenge the revocation in court. If followed properly, this process promotes fairness and accountability in land administration. However, continued misuse of the revocation power remains one of the major reasons why people distrust the Land Use Act, and it is an area that urgently needs reform.¹⁸²

4.7 Compensation on Land

Compensation is one of the most sensitive issues under the Land Use Act. When land is taken from an individual or community for public purposes, the owner is entitled to be compensated.

¹⁸⁰ Yakubu, Note 173.

¹⁸¹ 1991 4 NWLR PT 184 157 @195

¹⁸² *Ibid.*

This right is also protected under Section 44 of the 1999 Constitution (as amended), which guarantees every citizen the right to acquire and own immovable property anywhere in Nigeria and to receive prompt payment of compensation if such property is compulsorily acquired by the government. The principle is that no person should lose land to the government without being fairly compensated.

In the light of modern day, prompt compensation does not equate adequate compensation; as the compensation is limited the unexhausted improvements. By interpretation of the provision of *Section 29 of the Land Use Act*, the government is obliged to pay for compensation, where the land is required for public purpose, mining, oil pipelines or purposes connected thereof. Now the compensation as provided for in S. 29, it shall be the compensation for the value as at the date of revocation and unexhausted improvements as provided for in S. 28(2)(b) and 28(3)(c) of the Act. Consequently, where the provision of alternative accommodation is higher as determined by officers of the Land Use and Allocation committee is higher than the compensation payable under the Act, parties may agree that the excess in value in relation to the property shall be treated as a loan, wherein the person affected shall refund or repay to the government in the manner prescribed.

It is trite law that where there's a wrong, there's a remedy; the instrument for the pronouncement of justice is inherent in the judicial system. The constitution guarantees fair hearings in the matter of determination of the civil rights and obligations, including question or determinations by or against any government or authority to be determined by a court or other tribunal established by law.¹⁸³ In same vein, the access to court is guaranteed by the general provisions of S. 6(6)(b) and 272(1) of the Constitution¹⁸⁴, as property rights are expressly protected against unjustifiable governmental infringement under the 1999

¹⁸³ S.36 of the Constitution 1999 (as amended 2011)

¹⁸⁴ Ibid

constitution¹⁸⁵ The provisions Outlines that the judicial powers shall extend to matters between persons or government, to all actions, proceedings in relation to, for determination of any question as to civil rights and obligations. It's further illustrated in *Obikoya and Sons Ltd. V. The Governor of Lagos State and Anor*¹⁸⁶, when Nnaemeka -Agu JCA (as he then was) noted this

“.....In my view those civil rights and obligations include rights enjoyed over one's private property, movable or immovable.....the exercise of civil rights and obligations of any person implies that this ownership and enjoyment of his property should be held inviolate. The constitution itself guarantees and safeguards a person's right against compulsory acquisition of his property, except on certain conditions.

However, in practice, the compensation system in Nigeria is weak and often unfair. The Act limits compensation mainly to the value of improvements on the land, such as buildings, crops, or economic trees, rather than the full market value of the land itself. This means that where a person's undeveloped land is acquired, they may receive little or no compensation. Courts have recognized this as a major injustice, arguing that prompt payment does not necessarily mean adequate compensation. In modern land policy, “adequate” should mean fair market value that allows the displaced person to acquire another property of similar value.¹⁸⁷

Moreover, delays in payment and poor valuation methods make the situation worse. Many affected individuals wait years before receiving compensation, while others receive payments that are far below the real value of their property. These shortcomings not only create hardship but also discourage public trust in the land acquisition process.

Atinuke Fadeke Oluyemi “Revocation of Rights of Ocupancy: Legal Framework in Nigeria” Lagos State Ministry of Justice Law Review Series Copyright @2005

¹⁸⁶

Supra

R. Adeyemo, “Land Acquisition and Compensation Practices in Nigeria,” (2017) 61(1) *Journal of African Law* 45–63.

To improve the system, several reforms have been suggested. First, compensation should cover both the land and any developments on it. Second, valuation methods should be transparent and based on current market prices. Third, affected persons should have the right to challenge unfair assessments in an independent tribunal. Finally, compensation should be paid promptly and in a form that ensures real value, either in cash or through alternative land allocation. Implementing these reforms will bring fairness to the process and restore confidence in land governance under the LUA.¹⁸⁸

4.8 Prospect of the Land Use Act in relation to Individual Property Rights

Despite its inherent defects, the LUA still offers a workable foundation for land governance if its shortcomings are addressed through comprehensive and targeted reforms. One of the most promising areas of reform lies in the decentralization of land administration. Transferring land allocation authority from state governors to local land use allocation committees, as originally envisaged under the Act, could improve responsiveness to community-based needs and customary landholding systems, while also limiting arbitrariness and executive overreach in land administration.

Another important reform strategy is administrative modernization through digitization and statutory timelines. Although the LUA requires the Governor's consent for alienation of interests under Section 22, it fails to impose any timeline for such approval. In practice, this has led to bureaucratic delays and opportunities for corruption. Introducing clear, time-bound procedures, such as a twenty-eight-day maximum period for consent, and implementing digital systems for processing applications could enhance transparency and reduce transaction costs, thereby fostering a more efficient land market.

¹⁸⁸ *Ibid.*

There is also a compelling case for constitutional reform of the LUA's entrenched status. The Act is currently incorporated into the Constitution's Second Schedule, rendering it immune from amendment by ordinary legislative procedure. This has stifled reform and constrained its adaptability to evolving social, economic, and legal needs. Amending the Constitution to remove the LUA from its entrenched position would restore legislative competence to the National Assembly and empower it to revise outdated provisions while preserving essential principles of equitable land access.

Judicial interpretation also plays a vital role in safeguarding property rights within the LUA framework. Courts must continue to apply equitable principles such as legitimate expectation and procedural fairness in assessing revocations and compensations. In *Osho v Foreign Finance Corporation*,¹⁸⁹ the Supreme Court emphasized the importance of procedural compliance and fair notice in exercising revocation powers. Expanding on such jurisprudence would enhance judicial oversight and strengthen protection for right holders.

Equally important is reforming the LUA's compensation regime under Section 29, which restricts compensation to unexhausted improvements and disregards the land's inherent value. This often leaves affected persons inadequately compensated following revocation. Updating the valuation framework to include both land value and improvements would ensure more equitable outcomes and bring Nigeria closer to international standards of land justice and expropriation law.

The LUA also possesses latent potential to support affordable housing and inclusive urban development. If land banking powers are transparently and accountably managed, governments could utilize LUA provisions to allocate land for low-cost housing schemes, especially in urban areas grappling with population growth and housing deficits.

¹⁸⁹ Note 68.

In essence, the LUA need not remain a rigid tool of executive control. With progressive administrative reforms, judicial vigilance, and constitutional adjustments, the Act can evolve into a dynamic legal framework that promotes secure, equitable, and socially beneficial land tenure for all Nigerians.

4.9 Conclusion

The LUA, though conceived as a unifying framework for equitable land administration, has become a source of tension between state authority and individual property rights in Nigeria. By placing land ownership in the hands of the state governors and redefining private rights as mere occupancy rights, the Act effectively curtailed traditional and statutory proprietary rights. This centralization has bred bureaucratic inefficiency, corruption, and insecurity of tenure—particularly where revocation powers are exercised arbitrarily or compensation is inadequate. Moreover, the overlap between federal and state jurisdiction over land has created interpretative ambiguities that have been the subject of extensive litigation and judicial scrutiny.

Nonetheless, the LUA is not beyond redemption. Its underlying objectives remain relevant in a country striving for equitable development and orderly urbanization. However, achieving these goals requires robust legal reforms, including constitutional amendments to remove its entrenched status, administrative modernization to simplify consent procedures, and judicial activism to protect landholders from abuse. Integration of customary tenure systems and recognition of community rights would also enhance legitimacy and social justice. In the face of rising demand for land and persistent inequality, recalibrating the Act to balance public interest with private proprietary rights is not only necessary but imperative for sustainable development in Nigeria.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Research Findings

This study has examined in detail the evolution, legal foundations, and practical implications of proprietary rights in land within the context of Nigeria's Land Use Act of 1978. One of the central findings is that while the Act was promulgated with the intention of harmonizing and simplifying land administration across Nigeria, particularly by addressing the complexities of multiple tenure systems and by democratizing access to land, its implementation has often resulted in unintended consequences that undermine private proprietary rights.

Before the Act, landholding systems were diverse, with customary law playing a dominant role in communal land management, alongside statutory estates derived from English law. The Act introduced a new regime by vesting all land in each state in the Governor, thereby centralizing control. This centralization has had far-reaching consequences on the security of tenure, especially given the wide discretionary powers conferred on Governors regarding the grant, alienation, and revocation of land rights. The doctrine of estates was substantially modified, eliminating the concept of full ownership and replacing it with statutory or customary rights of occupancy. This shift has reduced the nature of proprietary interests from ownership to mere occupancy, subject to administrative oversight.

Additionally, the study finds that the procedure for revocation and compensation is not only susceptible to abuse but is often executed in a manner that violates constitutional safeguards. Section 44 of the 1999 Constitution (as amended) guarantees the right to property and requires that any compulsory acquisition must be in accordance with a law that provides for prompt payment of compensation. However, in practice, revocations for alleged public purposes frequently lack transparency, adequate compensation, and timely judicial review. Judicial

interpretations of the Land Use Act, although at times progressive, have not consistently upheld proprietary interests, further exacerbating uncertainty among landholders.

Again, the constitutional camouflage on the Act by virtue of its incorporation into the Constitution's Second Schedule¹⁹⁰, stifles reform and limits its adaptability to evolving needs and modern trends. That the subsequent provisions of S. 9(2)¹⁹¹ outlines the procedural structures for any alterations of the constitution in relation to the LUA; and amending the Constitution to extract the LUA from its entrenched position would empower the National Assembly on revision of most outdated provisions whilst preserving essential principles of equitable land access, being the intendment of the Act. Inevitably, an amendment of the Constitution, will amount to amendment of the LUA as both are interlaced. S. 315(5)(d)¹⁹²opines that:

*“Nothing in this constitution shall invalidate the following enactments, that is to say –
(d) the Land use Act
And the provisions of those enactments shall continue to apply and have full effect in accordance with their tenor and to the like extent as any other provisions forming part of this constitution and shall not be altered or repealed except in accordance with the provisions of Section 9 (2) of this constitution.”*

Furthermore, the research reveals that while the Act attempts to create uniformity in land administration, the pluralistic legal environment in Nigeria comprising customary, statutory, and Islamic law, continues to pose implementation challenges. This legal pluralism leads to inconsistent application, especially in rural areas where customary rights remain dominant but are not formally recognized under statutory procedures.

Moreover, the study uncovers a tension between public interest and individual proprietary rights. Although the state is empowered to acquire land for public purposes, the lack of clear definitions and objective standards for determining what constitutes "public purpose" often

¹⁹⁰ S. 315(5) (d), Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999(as amended 2011)

¹⁹¹ Supra

¹⁹² Supra

leads to misuse and land grabbing by political or economic elites. This threatens equitable access to land, a critical resource for socio-economic empowerment in a developing country like Nigeria.

Lastly, it is evident that the Act has not adequately adapted to the realities of modern urbanization, population growth, and economic development. Its provisions, crafted in 1978, no longer align with the complexities of contemporary land markets. Consequently, speculation, poor land documentation, and bureaucratic delays continue to frustrate efficient land use and secure proprietary rights.

5.2 Research Recommendations

- 1. Reform of Discretionary Powers:** The Land Use Act grants state governors' extensive discretionary powers, particularly concerning the grant, revocation, and regulation of rights of occupancy. This latitude, in the absence of clear statutory checks, has led to frequent abuse, arbitrary decision-making, and politically motivated land allocations. To ensure accountability and protect individual proprietary rights, these powers should be circumscribed by well-defined statutory guidelines. Additionally, the exercise of such powers should be subject to judicial oversight and administrative review mechanisms. This will promote transparency, enhance the credibility of land governance, and build public trust in the state's role as custodian of land.
- 2. Codification of Customary Land Rights:** A major challenge in Nigeria's land administration is the informal and often undocumented nature of customary land rights, which remain prevalent, especially in rural areas. To ensure legal certainty and protect landholders from dispossession, it is essential to formally recognize and codify these rights within the statutory framework. Customary rights of occupancy should be systematically documented, mapped, and integrated into the national land registry system. This approach would not only preserve indigenous landholding traditions but also facilitate land titling,

enable secure transactions, reduce land disputes, and promote access to credit for rural dwellers by making land a bankable asset.

3. **Clarification of ‘Public Purpose’:** The concept of “public purpose” under the Land Use Act is vague and susceptible to abuse, often serving as a pretext for compulsory acquisition that benefits private individuals or corporations under the guise of public interest. To protect proprietary rights and ensure genuine accountability, the term should be clearly defined in the Act, with an exhaustive list or well-delineated criteria for what qualifies as a public purpose. Moreover, independent oversight should be instituted to evaluate proposed acquisitions. Such reforms would ensure that compulsory acquisition powers are exercised in line with constitutional values and international best practices.
4. **Compensation and Access to Justice:** The current framework for compensation under the Land Use Act is inadequate, often resulting in payments that fall short of market value or are delayed indefinitely. This undermines the economic rights of affected persons and erodes confidence in the legal system. A revised compensation regime should be introduced that ensures prompt, adequate, and fair market-based compensation, including for unregistered and customary interests. Additionally, landholders must have unhindered access to effective legal remedies, including specialized tribunals or fast-track courts for land-related disputes. These reforms would strengthen the right to property and reduce grievances stemming from compulsory acquisitions.
5. **Review and Modernization of the Act:** Since its enactment in 1978, the Land Use Act has undergone minimal reform despite profound socio-economic changes in Nigeria. The Act’s provisions have become outdated and ill-suited to deal with challenges such as rapid urbanization, land scarcity, climate change, and speculative land hoarding. A comprehensive constitutional and legislative review of the Act is therefore necessary in relation to the provisions of *S. 315(5)(d) of the Second Schedule and 9(2) of the*

*Constitution*¹⁹³. Such review should aim to update terminologies, decentralize bureaucratic control, adopt digital land management systems, and incorporate environmental and gender-sensitive land policies. This modernization effort would realign the law with contemporary realities and support sustainable land governance in the 21st century.

5.3 Conclusion

The study has shown that while the LUA was a bold legislative attempt to consolidate land administration and ensure equitable access to land across Nigeria, its practical operation has largely failed to uphold the proprietary rights it sought to protect. The centralization of land ownership in the hands of state governors has created a power imbalance, leaving landholders vulnerable to arbitrary decisions, inadequate compensation, and legal uncertainty. This has led to a weakened proprietary framework that discourages investment, fosters insecurity of tenure, and inhibits land-based development initiatives.

Legal pluralism in Nigeria complicates the situation further, as the Act does not fully reconcile customary landholding practices with statutory regimes. The courts, while offering some redress, have not always provided a consistent jurisprudential standard to guide property rights under the Act. Moreover, the Act's outdated provisions no longer reflect the socio-economic and environmental dynamics of modern Nigeria.

Ultimately, for the LUA to fulfill its founding objective of equitable and effective land governance, comprehensive reform is essential. This includes limiting executive discretion, protecting individual proprietary interests, recognizing customary systems, and ensuring access to justice. A reformed land administration framework must strike a balance between the state's role in public interest and the inviolability of individual rights, which is essential for sustainable development, investment security, and the protection of fundamental rights.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

¹⁹³ as amended 2011

BOOKS

1. The Land Use Act, 1978 Cap L5, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria (LFN) 2004.
2. Atinuke Fadeke Oluyemi, *Revocation of Rights of Occupancy: Legal Framework in Nigeria*, Lagos State Ministry of Justice Review Series, Copyright @ 2005.
3. The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended 2011).
4. Hon. Justice I. A. Umezulike, OFR, FCIARB., *ABC of Contemporary Land Law in Nigeria (revised and enlarged edition)* Copyright @ 2013 ISBN 978-978-910-267-9
5. I.O. Smith, *Practical Approach to Law of Real Property in Nigeria* (Lagos: Ecowatch Publication Limited, 2007) 2.
6. J. Locke, *Two Treatises of Government* (Peter Laslett edn, Cambridge University Press, 1988) 34.
7. J. Bentham, *An Introduction to the Principles of Morals and Legislation* (Oxford University Press 1907) 46.
8. Hanach Dagan, *A Liberal Theory of Property* (Cambridge University Press April 2021) 24. ISBN 9781108290340, Publication @ March 2021.
9. Crown Lands Ordinance of 1902.
10. Land and Native Rights Ordinance of 1916.
11. Native Lands Acquisition Ordinance of 1917.
12. T.B. Nadler and P. Evans-Jones (eds), *Unjustified Enrichment: Key Issues in Comparative Perspective* (Cambridge University Press, 2002) 71.
13. B. Ibhawoh, *Human Rights in Africa: The Politics of Land Reform* (Cambridge University Press 2014) 14.
14. Minerals and Mining Act 2007.
15. African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (adopted 27 June 1981, entered into force 21 October 1986) 1520 UNTS 217.
16. Lagos State Land Registration Law 2015.
17. African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act Cap A9 LFN 2004.
18. Harold J. Laski, *A Grammar of Politics* (George Allen and Unwin Publishers Ltd. Boston and Sydney, 1967) Chapter 5 at P. 173.
19. Property and Conveyancing Law 1959.
20. The Lagos State Urban and Regional Planning Board Law, Cap L52, Laws of Lagos State 2003, 2010.

21. S. 108(1) (a) Cap. 100 Laws of Western Nigeria 1959.
22. J. A. Yakubu, *Land Law in Nigeria* (Macmillan Publishers, 2019) p. 142.

JOURNALS

1. C. C. Opata & O. Asogwa, "Title, Rituals, and Land Use: The Heritage of a Nigerian Society." (2017) 7(2) *Sage Open* 2158244016689129.
2. F. k. Upham, "The Paradoxical Roles of Property Rights in Growth and Development." (2015) 8(2) *Law and Development Review* 253-269.
3. T.O. Elias, *Nigerian Land Law and Custom* (Online: Taylor & Francis, 2024) 2.
4. A. Otubu, "The Land Use Act and Land Administration in 21st Century Nigeria: Need for Reforms." (2018) 9(1) *Journal of Sustainable Development Law and Policy* 80-108.
5. K.H. Babalola & S.A. Hull, "Examining the Land Use Act of 1978 and Its Effects on Tenure Security in Nigeria: A Case Study of Ekiti State, Nigeria." (2019) 22(1) *Potchefstroom Electronic Law Journal* 1-14.
6. F. Obeng-Odoom, "Land Reforms in Africa: Theory, Practice, and Outcome" (2016) 49(5) *Habitat International* 923.
7. M.E. Nwocha, "Impact of the Nigerian Land Use Act on Economic Development in the Country." (2016) 8(2) *Acta Universitatis Danubius. Administratio* 117-128.
8. World Bank, *Doing Business 2020: Comparing Business Regulation in 190 Economies* (World Bank Group, 2020) <https://www.doingbusiness.org/content/dam/doingBusiness/media/Annual-Reports/English/DB2020-report_web-version.pdf> accessed 15 May 2025.
9. O. O. Makinde, & O. T. Makinde, "Public Land Acquisition and Administration in Nigeria: Issues, Strategies and Policies." (2019) 6(7) *Journal of Multidisciplinary Engineering Science and Technology* 10381-10394
10. A. Otubu, 'The Land Use Act and Land Ownership Debate in Nigeria: A Critical Review: Resolving the Impasse' (SSRN Electronic Journal, 2015) <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/272173374_The_Land_Use_Act_and_Land_Ownership_Debate_in_Nigeria_Resolving_the_Impasse> accessed 15 May 2025.
11. A. Otubu, "The Land Use Act and Land Administration in 21st Century Nigeria: Need for Reforms" (2018) 9(1) *Journal of Sustainable Development Law and Policy* 80-108.
12. A. N. Niyazova et al., "Land Proprietary Rights and Limitations in Private and Public Interests" (2016) 7(3) *Journal of Advanced Research in Law and Economics* 584-589.

13. K. H. Babalola and SA Hull, “*Examining the Land Use Act of 1978 and its Effects on Tenure Security in Nigeria: A Case Study of Ekiti State, Nigeria*” (2019) 22(1) *Potchefstroom Electronic Law Journal/Potchefstroomse Elektroniese Regsblad* 21-30.
14. C.U. Ugonabo, CC Egolum and RO Sado, “*Nigerian Land Policy: Issues, Challenges and the Way Forward*” (2023) 11(1) *Global Journal of Politics and Law Research* 57-77.
15. O.F. Kasim and SB Agbola, “*Strategies and Challenges of Land Reform in Nigeria*” (2018) 53(2) *Journal of Public Administration* 541-564.
16. A. L. Mabogunje, “*Land Reform in Nigeria: Progress, Problems & Prospects*” In *Annual Conference on Land Policy and Administration (World Bank, April, 2010)* 26.
17. A.K. Otubu, “*Land Reforms and the Future of Land Use Act in Nigeria*” (2007-2010) *Nigerian Current Law Review (NIALS)* 226-143.
18. T.S. Kumari and GI Priyadarsini, “*Concept of Property-Jurisprudential Perspective*” (2019) *GLS Law Journal* 7-17.
19. A. Ilori and A.K. Adebayo, “*Customary Land Tenure System and the Land Use Act: A Comparative Analysis*” (2019) 1 *International Review of Law and Jurisprudence* 92.
20. F.K.F. Byamugisha and N. Dubosse, “*The Investment Case for Land Tenure Security in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Cost–Benefit Analysis*” (2023) 14 *Journal of Benefit-Cost Analysis* 272–300.
21. B. M. Salawu, “*Harnessing Customary Land Tenure for Sustainable Resource Management in Rural Nigeria*” (2025) 11 *NIULJS* 1
22. M. I. O. Nwogu, “*Ownership and Possession of Land under the Nigerian Customary Land Tenure System: A Legal Appraisal*” (2023) 19(2) *Unizik Law Journal* 1-12.
23. O. Lewis, “*Resolving the Problem of Land Ownership in Nigeria*” (2025) 33(1) *African Journal of International and Comparative Law* 142-165.
24. Lusina Ho, “*Unjust Enrichment and Equity*” in *Research Handbook on Unjust Enrichment and Restitution* (Edward Elgar Publishing, 2020) 123-144.
25. UN-Habitat, *The State of African Cities 2015: Urbanization and Economic Growth* (United Nations Human Settlements Programme 2015).
26. I. Nwosu, “*Governance, Land and Equity in Nigeria’s Urban Development*” (2016) 7(3) *Nigerian Journal of Sustainable Development Law and Policy* 112
27. T. T. Oladokun, “*Improving Land Governance in Nigeria: The Case of Compulsory Acquisition and Compensation Practice*” (2023) 17 *Journal of Civil Engineering and Architecture* 251-257.

28. T. Ajala, “*Gender Discrimination in Land Ownership and the Alleviation of Women’s Poverty in Nigeria: A Call for New Equities*” (2017) 17(1) *International Journal of Discrimination and the Law* 51-66.
29. Amnesty International, *Nigeria: Forced Evictions in Abuja Make Thousands Homeless* (Amnesty International, 2008).
30. S Nwatu and C Ajibo, “*Compulsory Acquisition of Land (Private Property) in Nigeria: Prioritizing Public Interest over Private Interest*” (2021) 16 *The Nigerian Juridical Review* 275-289.
31. R. A. Adeogun and S.O. Oni, “*Ownership and Compulsory Acquisition under Customary Land Tenure in South-West Nigeria: A Legal and Socio-Cultural Analysis*” (2025) 8 *African Journal of Law, Political Research and Administration* 1–12.
32. I. Adewumi and F. Olokesusi, “*Land Reform in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects*” (2011) *NISER Monograph Series, Ibadan* 1-9.
33. UN-Habitat, *The State of African Cities 2020: Managing Urban Land* (United Nations 2020).
34. A. O. Agboola and A.R. Amidu, “*Rethinking Effective Urban Land Governance in Sub-Saharan Africa: Moving Towards a Transcendental Critical Realist Approach*” (2023) 34 *Urban Forum* 253–269.
35. O. L. Makinde, O.O. Alawode and R.A. Olaoye, “*Legal Issues in Land Acquisition for Agricultural Production in Nigeria*” (2024) 8(2) *American Journal of Agricultural Science, Engineering, and Technology* 1–9.
36. Joseph Oyedeji, “*Assessment of Land Speculator’s Operation for Land Accessibility in Nigeria*” (2022) 10(1) *Baltic Journal of Real Estate Economics and Construction Management* 26–40
37. AT Abayomi, “*Analysing the Concept of Right of Occupancy under the Nigeria Land Use Act*” (2022) 3 *Jus Corpus Law Journal* 1065.
38. A. Adeyinka and A. Adedolapo, “*The Certificate of Occupancy as a Conclusive Proof of Title: Fact or Fiction*” (SSRN, January 17, 2019) <<https://ssrn.com/abstract=3324775>> accessed 25 June 2025.
39. K. Balarabe, “*Open Grazing Legislations and the Protection of Ethnic Minority Rights in Nigeria*” (2021) 25(10) *The International Journal of Human Rights* 1835-1856.
40. Chaman Law Firm, ‘*Land Use Act and Land Tenure Systems; The Land Use Act Vs Traditional Land Tenure*’ (Chaman Law Firm, n.d) <<https://chamanlawfirm.com/land-use-act-and-land-tenure-systems/?>> accessed 25 June 2025.

41. C. Uwaegbulam, 'Land Use Act: Between Powerful Governors and Oppressed Citizenry' (The Guardian, 29 June 2023) <<https://guardian.ng/news/land-use-act-between-powerful-governors-and-oppressed-citizenry/>> accessed 25 June 2025.
42. A. S. Aina, 'Governor's Consent in Nigeria Land Law: Issues and Challenges' <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/386342446_GOVERNOR'S_CONSENT_IN_NIGERIA_LAND_LAW_ISSUES_AND_CHALLENGES> accessed 25 June 2025.
43. The Guardian, 'Gbadamosi seeks repeal of Land Use Act' (9 December 2019) <<https://guardian.ng/news/gbadamosi-seeks-repeal-of-land-use-act/>> accessed 25 June 2025.
44. O. E. Uzoamaka, N.C. Chisom and U.A. Nnamdi, "Critique of Nigerian Land Use Act of 1978" (2021) 11(6) *International Journal of Engineering Science* 28115-28120.
45. A. A. Izinyon, 'The Unending Battle on the Validity of Lack of Governor's Consent Under the Land Use Act: Has The Common Law Rule of Equity Resolved this?' (Alexizinyon, 28 June 2025) <alexizinyon.com/2020/10/09/the-unending-battle-on-the-validity-of-lack-of-governors-consent-under-the-land-use-act-has-the-common-law-rule-of-equity-resolved-this/> accessed 25 June 2025.
46. R. Ajayi, "Legal Constraints to Effective Land Use in Nigeria" (2021) 19 *African Research Review* 224.
47. I.O. Odionu and I.K. Oraegbunam, "The Status of Certificate of Occupancy under the Land Registration Law 2015 of Lagos State: A Wake-up Call on Other States in Nigeria" (2021) 3 *International Journal of Comparative Law and Legal Philosophy* 50.
48. UK Property Law Expertise <<https://property-practice-law-sqe.co.uk/land-law-in-the-uk-a-comprehensive-guide-to-key-principles-and-legislation/>> accessed 14 July, 2025.
49. Land Rights Legislation - [Agreements, Treaties and Negotiated Settlements](https://www.atns.net.au/land-rights-legislation-1#) <<https://www.atns.net.au/land-rights-legislation-1#>> accessed 16th July, 2025.
50. Oyo state Government has concluded arrangement with UACN property to build houses for the low- and middle-class income earners, see Oyo State bulletin No. 18 (2014).
51. Income Tax Department (Government of India), 'Joint Development Agreements (JDA) Tutorials, 2025' <<https://incometaxindia.gov.in/tutorials/66.joint-development-agreements.pdf>> accessed 20 October 2025.
52. R. Adeyemo, "Land Acquisition and Compensation Practices in Nigeria," (2017) 61(1) *Journal of African Law* 45–63.

